

Proposed Standard for Neonatologist Performed Lung Ultrasound

Erik Küng¹, Bernhard Schwabberger²,
Viktoria Gruber², Natascha
Pramhofer³, Mathias Klemme⁴,
Michael Schneider¹, Lisa Habrina¹,
Tobias Werther¹, Lukas Aichhorn¹

¹ Medical University Vienna, Comprehensive Center for Pediatrics, Department of Pediatrics and Adolescent Medicine, Division of Neonatology, Intensive Care Medicine and Neuropediatrics, Währinger Gürtel 18-20, 1090 Vienna, Austria

² Medical University Graz, Department of Paediatrics and Adolescent Medicine, Division of Neonatology, Auenbruggerplatz 34/II, 8036 Graz, Austria

³ Johannes Kepler University, Medical Faculty, Kepler University Hospital, Department of Neonatology, Krankenhausstraße 26-30, 4021 Linz, Austria

⁴ Ludwig-Maximilian University Munich, Klinikum Großhadern, Marchioninstr. 15, 81377 Munich, Germany

version 5.8
October 9, 2024

Contents

1	Methods	4
1.1	Screened Literature	4
2	Introduction	6
2.1	Indications	6
2.2	Limitations	7
2.3	Users and Training	8
2.4	Instructors	8
3	Technique	9
3.1	Safety	9
3.2	Ultrasound Probe	9
3.3	Recommended Settings	10
4	Exam	11
4.1	Views	11
5	Documentation	14
5.1	Medical History and Clinical Information	14
5.2	Minimal Documentation of Lung Ultrasound	14
5.3	Transparency and Reproducibility	14
6	Animal studies	15
7	Elements of Lung Ultrasound	16
7.1	Anatomy	16
7.2	Signs	16
7.3	BLUE Protocol - D. Lichtenstein [1]	25
7.4	Semiquantitative Assessment	27
7.5	Atelectasis Depth	32
7.6	Diaphragm	32

8	Diagnostic Findings in Lung Ultrasound (alphabetic)	34
8.1	Physiological Findings	34
8.2	Pathological Findings in Lung Ultrasound	34
9	Lung Ultrasound in Critical Situations	56
10	Lung Ultrasound and Procedures	57
10.1	Weaning from Extracorporeal Membrane Oxygenation	57
10.2	Targeted Ventilation using Lung Ultrasound	57
10.3	Targeted Therapy using Lung Ultrasound	59
10.4	Lung Ultrasound after Central Venous Line Placement	60
10.5	Lung Ultrasound and Thoracic Ultrasound in Cases of Non Accidental Injury	61
11	Implementation and Digitalisation of Lung Ultrasound	62
11.1	Implementation	62
11.2	Digitalisation	62
12	Outlook	63
12.1	Lung Ultrasound and Electric Impedance Tomography	63
12.2	Surfactant need	63
12.3	Artificial Intelligence	63
12.4	Cardiopulmonary Ultrasound	63
	Bibliography	64
	Appendix	90
	Abbreviation	91

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank Stefan Reithmayr, whose help, experience and expertise contributed significantly to the preparation of this document, as well as Ulrike Salzer-Muhar, who initiated the implementation of lung ultrasound in neonates at the Department for Neonatology, Pediatric Intensive Care and Neuropediatrics of the Medical University of Vienna.

Chapter 1

Methods

This document defines a standard for lung ultrasound as a point-of-care ultrasound in neonatology, a "Neonatologist Performed Lung Ultrasound - NPLUS" [2]. The term NPLUS emphasizes the functional and integrative character of the examination, as it is performed at the bedside by the involved neonatologist, who interprets the results in consideration of the patient's clinical condition. On a regular basis the most recent publications are screened and evaluated in context with clinical practice as well as experience.

This is an integrative review of the literature published until 26.8.2023 including posters, discussions and presentations from relevant meetings and conferences as well as experiences of experts in the field. For this purpose the platform pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov was searched with the query "(lung OR thoracic) AND ultrasound AND (neonate OR infant)". Titles and abstracts were independently reviewed for relevance by two experts in the field (experience in lung ultrasound over 2 years). In case of discrepancies, a third expert decided.

Clinical experience and practical comments were added to the content after critical review by the authors.

1.1 Screened Literature

Table 1.1: Screened and included number (n) of papers for each version starting with v4.

Version	Screened	Included	Unavailable
4	580	79	NA
5	500	125	3

Chapter 2

Introduction

Neonatologist performed lung ultrasound (NPLUS) is a tool for dynamic assessment of lung diseases and diseases with lung involvement and can be used for visualization during various procedures and interventions. The interpretation of findings from lung ultrasound must take into account the patient's current clinical situation and history. Only with this context can appropriate treatment be initiated or continued. It is a simple examination technique that, when used correctly and with knowledge of its limitations, can provide rapid answers to specific questions. Almost all chest disorders occur in contact with the pleura. This explains the potential of lung ultrasound [3]. Implementation of lung ultrasound at a neonatal intensive care unit reduces [4], even halves [5] the number or nearly diminishes the need [6] of chest X-rays with significant reduction of radiation dose per patient [4, 5, 6]. A systematic review performed during the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic showed that the use of lung ultrasound can be seen complementary to clinical and laboratory assessment and is a corner stone in the care of respiratory infections [7]. At the University of Manitoba, lung ultrasound has been established as the first-line diagnostic method in neonates with suspected pulmonary diseases since 2016 [8]; at two large Chinese NICUs since 2017 [9, 10]. The Introduction of lung ultrasound as the primary diagnostic method led to a reduction in the use of ventilators by 40.2%, a reduction of mechanical ventilation duration of 67.5% and no more weaning failure [10]. In Italian NICUs, 82% have adopted the lung ultrasound with 23% referring to use it as the first-choice diagnostic imaging test [11]. Whereas in the United Kingdom, only 6% reported the routine use of lung ultrasound [12].

2.1 Indications

Lung ultrasound can be performed with high accuracy and good agreement with chest radiographs for the detection of various intrathoracic pathologies; the overall Kappa was 0.749 [13] showing substantial agreement between the two modalities. Lung ultrasound

is indicated in the following situations:

- Suspected respiratory distress syndrome [14, 15]
- Acute cardiorespiratory deterioration [14]
- Assessment after acute deterioration [14]
- Suspected pneumothorax
- Assessment during mechanical ventilation [14]
- Suspected atelectasis or dystelectasis / loss of aeration
- Assessment in patients with increased oxygen requirement
- Persistent pulmonary hypertension of the newborn [16]
- Assessment after cardiac surgery
- Suspected congenital pulmonary airway malformation [14, 17]
- Assessment after placement of central venous line
- Assessment before transfer [18]
- Assessment during transfer [19]
- Assessment of ventilation during extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO) [20]
- Assessment in situations without further imaging
- Suspected pneumonia / bronchiolitis [7, 15]
- Assessment for lung edema [15]
- Assessment for tuberculosis [21]

2.2 Limitations

Up until now, pulmonary hyperinflation and pulmonary interstitial as well as bullous emphysema can not be visualized in ultrasound but both play a crucial role in neonatology [22]. This must be considered when only lung ultrasound is used.

Most lung ultrasound studies are performed in high income countries with experienced operators. It is not clear whether the results are transferable to low- and middle-income countries [23]. However, small feasibility studies indicate that good reliability may also be achieved in low and middle income countries [23].

2.3 Users and Training

2.3.1 Users

Lung ultrasound can be performed by doctors, nurses and respiratory therapists alike. Pediatricians achieve high interobserver correlation with radiologists in diagnosing bronchiolitis in children [24].

In neonatology, a theoretical course and 20-25 supervised [8, 25] with a total of 30 lung ultrasounds [25] are sufficient for an adequate inter-rater reliability with chest-X-ray [25]. Around 66 % of practitioners learn this technique through self-training [11].

Especially in pediatric critical care adequate training is essential: it was shown that a 2-day course only achieves agreement with experts in 56 % of cases [26]. But in pediatric residents a 6 h e-learning course followed by a 2 h practical course showed substantial agreement in detecting A-lines, and near perfect agreement for nonhomogeneous B-lines, coalescent B-lines and pleural effusion [27]. Guitart et al. showed that a theoretical course with exam followed by thirty supervised studies with exam ensures excellent agreement in the detection of pneumonia [28].

In nurses, theoretical training for 12 h followed by practice for 45 h was successfully used to recognize intrathoracic structures (i.e. aortic arch, right pulmonary artery, trachea, lung sliding and esophagus) with an accuracy of 80-100 % [29].

In respiratory therapists, theoretical training followed by a workshop and 20 supervised studies resulted in an excellent inter-rater agreement [30].

Overall, inter-rater reliability is high [25, 31]; between novices (6 months experience), users (1 year experience) and experienced (5 year experience) [31]. The use of a non-linear probe causes lower inter-rater reliability [31].

Training can be performed in high-fidelity simulation [32].

2.4 Instructors

There is no definition or certification process for a lung ultrasound instructor.

At the university of Manitoba, Canada, the instructor status is achieved after one year of application and 50 performed lung ultrasound scans of good quality for doctors [8] and respiratory therapists alike [30].

Chapter 3

Technique

3.1 Safety

Mechanical index should be below 0.3 and neither contrast agents nor shear wave elastography is recommended [33, 34]. An *in situ* mechanical index of >0.48 is the threshold for pulmonary hemorrhage in rats [34]. An *in situ* mechanical index of 0.35-0.49 was safe [35].

Lung ultrasound can be performed in babies and children with bronchiolitis without sedation [24].

3.2 Ultrasound Probe

Every probe can be used for lung ultrasound [36, 37]. The use of a linear probe [38] with a frequency of at least 7.5 MHz [39], 9 MHz [14], 10 MHz [38, 40, 41], but mostly with 12-14 MHz [41, 42] is recommended.

Higher frequencies result in more B-lines, but overall conformity and reliability is excellent with different frequencies [43].

If there is no linear probe available, a high frequency convex probe with at least 8 MHz can be used [14], but using a non-linear probe in neonates causes lower inter-rater reliability, especiall in unexperienced users [31]. In children, a convex probe may have advantages over a linear probe [38, 44].

The probe must be disinfected before and after every examination as defined by the local guidelines [14, 41].

Many ultrasound machines now have a lung preset; if this is not available small parts or a similar program used to display muscles are good alternatives. Additional software filters should not be used, because they can reduce or change artifacts and movement artifacts you are looking for.

3.2.1 Wireless Probe

The recent development of wireless probes allows for easy examination of isolated patients and live assessment of ultrasound images by a supervisor [45].

3.3 Recommended Settings

- Lung; otherwise: small parts
- 4-5 cm depth [37, 41, 42]
- Set focus zone to pleural line.
- Activate CRI (Crossbeam) at level 2 to increase contrast and resolution.
- Deactivate Harmonics, speckle reduction, sono-CT and XRES.

Chapter 4

Exam

The entire examination can be performed in the supine position [14, 38, 39, 41, 42]. The posterior areas can also be evaluated this way by tilting them slightly upwards or the patient can be brought in lateral position. The examination is also feasible in prone position [8, 41, 42] or lateral position [41, 42]. Immediately after position change, false high scores might occur which level off after 1 h [8, 46].

The examination is possible during ECMO [20, 47, 48].

The examination takes 2 minutes on average by an experienced health care provider [49]. For special indications—like neonatal pneumonia—extended examination in supine and prone position should be considered.

4.1 Views

The views are performed in sagittal plane orthogonal to the thorax and ribs (vertical) in at least six anatomical areas [41]. Apart from the standard views it is essential that every area of the lung is examined for at least one breathing cycle; as some conditions are only visible in inspiration or expiration.

Particularly in the lateral and posterior areas, it is important to place the transducer exactly orthogonal to the pleural line. If there is a tilt, the pleura seems thickened and the number of B-lines is increased and debris sign might be visible.

If abnormalities are detected, the transducer is rotated 90° to visualize and verify them in the transverse plane (horizontal) or in the intercostal space parallel to the ribs [41]. Abnormalities are documented in at least two planes.

Figure 4.1: Example of a intercostal view.

4.1.1 Thoracal Views

6-region method [14, 39, 41, 42]

- Right posterior: right paravertebral to posterior axillary line
- Right lateral: right posterior to anterior axillary line
- Right anterior: right anterior axillary to parasternal line
- Left anterior: left parasternal to anterior axillary line
- Left lateral: left anterior to posterior axillary line
- Left posterior: left posterior axillary to paravertebral line

12-region method [14, 38, 41, 42, 50]

Each region from the 6-region method is divided into a cranial and a caudal view by the mamillary line [14].

4.1.2 Transabdominal views

The lung bases can be visualized via transabdominal views in the sagittal or transverse plane. The liver or spleen are used as ultrasound windows to assess the *Pars diaphragmatica* [38]. Shen et al. even included the lung base in a modified score using the same

Figure 4.2: Example of a posterior view.

Figure 4.3: Example of a lateral view.

Figure 4.4: Example of an anterior view.

graduation as most other studies (see Chapter 7.4.1) but applied on the abdominal views [51].

Chapter 5

Documentation

5.1 Medical History and Clinical Information

Lung ultrasound is a tool to address clinical questions. Accordingly, information relevant to a diagnosis or clinical condition should be documented: age, weight, mode of ventilation, previous intervention and the indication for the examination.

5.2 Minimal Documentation of Lung Ultrasound

At least 6 areas should be documented, each with at least one B-Scan and corresponding labeling. If the child's thorax is too large for the transducer, the area must be divided into 2 cross-sectional images (cranial and caudal) according to the 12-region method (see chapter 4.1.1) and labeled accordingly.

5.3 Transparency and Reproducibility

To ensure transparency and reproducibility, all features specific to a diagnosis are documented in addition to the minimum documentation. The position of the patient should be specified for result interpretation [3]. Abnormalities are documented in two planes (see section 4.1). If the size of an abnormality is relevant, it is measured and documented in two planes at its maximum extent.

The best way to document are video loops of at least 3 s duration.

Chapter 6

Animal studies

Lung ultrasound can monitor lung aeration [52, 53, 54] and liquid clearance after birth in near-term lambs [53] and detects changes in lung volume [55]. Lung ultrasound can be used in a bovine model of bronchiolitis [56].

In rabbits, lung ultrasound findings correspond to extravascular lung water concentration [57].

In a neonatal model of acute respiratory distress syndrome in piglets, lung ultrasound score was able to predict severity of injury especially in the posterior ares [58].

Chapter 7

Elements of Lung Ultrasound

7.1 Anatomy

The thorax consists of skin, subcutaneous tissue, and muscles above and between the ribs. Beneath the ribs is the parietal and pulmonic pleura located, which slide against each other with each breath. Many interlobular septa lie within the pulmonic pleura and separate the individual lobes, which consist of many air-filled acini. [40]

7.2 Signs

Lung ultrasound signs vary little by age [59].

7.2.1 Pleural Line

The pleural line is a slightly bent, echogenic, smooth and thin line [14,38,39,40,42,60,61] (Figure 7.1). It occurs as a result of the reflection due to the different acoustic impedances of pleura and lung tissue [14]. If there is liquid between the pulmonic and parietal pleura, the two can be visualized separately [62].

Unossified ribs are anechoic round areas. However ossified ribs produce an acoustical

Figure 7.1: Picture of a pleural line.

Figure 7.2: Picture of lung sliding.

shadow. [62,63] Two ossified ribs, their acoustical shadows and the pleural line inbetween them are called the bat sign. The bat sign guarantees correct positioning of the probe. In neonates this sign is not visible in the anterior parts of the lung, because the ribs are not ossified yet and therefore no shadow is visible [40,61].

The pleural line develops roughly after the first 4 breaths of a newborn. The lung is collapsed at the beginning and fills with air breath by breath [64]. After the initial ventilation, interstitial fluid continues to be present, visible as an increased number of B-lines or a white lung.

After this initial ventilation, there continues to be increased interstitial fluid, visible as increased B-lines or even a white lung. This increased interstitial fluid is typically reabsorbed within 4 hours [65].

Interpretation

The condition of the pleural line is assessed: regular (thin and smooth), thickened, irregular (rough).

Pleural Thickness

The exact thickness of the pleura depends on the fat content of the tissue (body mass index), as this has an influence on the acoustic impedance of the tissue [66]. In addition it depends on the frequency of the transducer [66]. In healthy newborns and preterm infants, pleural thickness is <1 mm in the first 24 h [67] and in children <5 mm [38]. In clinical practice, pleural thickness is highly variable and depends in particular on the angle of the transducer to the pleural line.

7.2.2 Lung Line

Line representing pulmonal pleura in case of pleural effusion [60].

7.2.3 Lung Sliding

Lung sliding is the sliding of the pulmonal pleura against the parietal pleura at each breath [14, 38, 39, 40, 42, 44, 61, 63] (Figure 7.2). The thoracic wall does not move or moves in the opposite direction to the sliding motion [63]. This dynamic phenomenon

Figure 7.3: Picture of a seashore sign.

Figure 7.4: Picture of a stratosphere sign.

manifests as movement of the Z-lines (Chapter 7.2.10) and B-lines (Chapter 7.2.6) and excludes pneumothorax. More lung sliding is visible at the lung bases with a progressive decrease towards the apex [63].

The absence of lung sliding is pathological [14].

Seashore Sign

The seashore sign corresponds to the sandy beach sign. In M-mode, parallel lines appear in the area above the pleura (Sea) and as a noise below the pleura (Shore) (figure 7.3). Reminiscent of a pictogram of a beach, hence seashore sign.

It is a sign of a ventilated lung. [14, 40, 61, 63]

Stratosphere Sign

The stratosphere sign corresponds to the barcode sign. In M-mode, parallel lines appear in the area above and below the pleura [14, 40, 61] (Figure 7.4). Reminiscent of a pictogram of a sky, hence stratosphere sign. It corresponds to the absence of lung sliding and indicates the presence of a pneumothorax, but may also be present in congenital pulmonary airway malformation (CPAM), pneumatocele, marked hyperinflation, or interstitial or subcutaneous emphysema.

Figure 7.5: Picture of a lung point.

Lung Point

The point in B-mode and M-mode between lung sliding and no lung sliding; at which lung sliding and no lung sliding alternate with each breath [14, 39] (Figure 7.5) is called lung point. In M-mode, this is the point between stratosphere sign and seashore sign. This point migrates with each breath as the lung advances into the pneumothorax area. It is best to show the lung point in the transverse plane (horizontal) to facilitate positional relationship to the anterior, middle, and posterior axillary lines.

7.2.4 Lung Pulse

The lung pulse is a pulsation of the pleura (similar to lung sliding but of much lower amplitude) or consolidation synchronous with the heart rate, which does not correspond to lung sliding [14, 50, 68]. In M-mode, parallel lines appear in the area above the pleura; below the pleura, also parallel lines appear, which are interrupted synchronously with every heart beat [68]. If the lung is getting more and more solid, the lung pulse gets more and more visible, but its role in detecting pathologies is unclear [62].

Lung pulse might be a sign for complete atelectasis [39].

Because of the relative proximity to the heart, this sign is difficult to interpret in neonates [62].

7.2.5 A-Line

A-lines are horizontal, hyperechogenic, equidistant, smooth lines below the pleural line [14, 39, 40, 42, 44, 60, 69] (figure 7.6). These are reverberation artifacts caused by repetitively reflected sound waves between the transducer, hyperechogenic lines (e.g. line between fat and muscle tissue) and pleura [14, 39, 40, 42, 61, 63, 66, 66]. Due to reverberation it takes ultrasound waves longer (two times, three times, etc.) to return, the device calculates A-lines as a mirrored pleural line equidistant (multiplied) below the pleural plane. A-lines are indicative of a ventilated area [42].

Figure 7.6: Picture of A-Lines.

Figure 7.7: Picture of B-Lines.

The A-Lines can be numbered starting with A1, A2 and so on [60]. If lines in similar length are visible inbetween, they are named A',A'' and so on [60].

7.2.6 B-Line

B-lines are discrete vertical hyperechogenic ring-down artifacts [66, 70, 71] that arise from the pleural line, move to the bottom of the screen without fading, and move in synchrony with lung sliding [14, 39, 42, 44, 61, 63, 69, 72] (Figure 7.7). They erase the A-lines [42]. B-lines occur physiologically and are a sign of interstitial fluid in the interstitial or alveolar compartment [38, 63, 70] or may be present due to scarring [44]. B-lines arise from the pulmonary pleura and thereby prove that the two pleura sheets are adjacent [70]. On the first day after birth B-lines are physiologically increased, but decrease within 24 h [44, 63, 73] and usually disappear by day three [63] [44, 73]. The physiological B-lines postnatally can be postnatally seen mainly in the posterior [74] and basal areas [73, 74].

The number of B-lines is dependent on the probe [70] and the frequency used [43].

Septal Rockets

3-4 B-lines per intercostal space (ICS) are called septal rockets. Septal rockets correlate with thickened subpleural interlobular septa [75].

Glass Rockets

5-12 B-lines per intercostal space are called glass rockets. Glass rockets correlate with ground-glass opacities in CT scans and are a sign of severe interstitial syndrome [66, 75].

Coalescent B-lines

Numerous, merging B-lines that are impossible to clearly enumerate in the whole intercostal space [14] and are not countable. This is a sign of interstitial syndrome [14], alveolar syndrome, bronchiolitis, transient tachypnoea of the newborn and respiratory distress syndrome.

White Lung

The definition of a white lung are coalescent B-lines in all areas [14, 39] resulting in a literal white image in every view. This is a sign of interstitial syndrome, alveolar syndrome, transitory tachypnoea of the newborn [14] and respiratory distress syndrome.

Interpretation of B-lines

Musolino et al. postulated, that cardiogenic B-lines can be differentiated from pneumogenic B-lines [38]. While cardiogenic B-lines are located in septal position without consolidation or pleural abnormalities [76] and do change with positioning, pneumogenic B-lines are associated with pleural abnormalities and do not change with positioning [38]. The cardiogenic B-lines can be visible due to hemodynamic changes during sepsis [76]. In our experience, a differentiation of cardiogenic and pneumogenic B-lines is difficult. The number and the morphology of B-lines depend on the preset as well as the probe. Furthermore, the ESPNIC guidelines for POCUS stated, that lung ultrasound can not differentiate between cardiogenic and non-cardiogenic B-lines.

Diuretic Therapy

The number of B-lines decreases if diuretics are started in patients with pulmonary edema or bronchopulmonary dysplasia [77, 78].

7.2.7 Dialysis

In adults, the number of B-lines prior to dialysis was able to identify fluid overload more accurately than chest-X-ray or physical examination [79]. The optimal cut-off for fluid overload was ≥ 15 B-lines. The B-lines were determined following a standardized 28-position B-line score consisting of a scanning from the second to fifth intercostal space on the right side and from the second to fourth space on the left side, in the parasternal, midclavicular, anterior axillary and midaxillary positions for a total of 28 positions. At every scanning site in each intercostal space, B-lines are counted from 0 to 10. It is currently accepted that, with a 28-position score, a B-line score of ≤ 5 is indicative of euvolemia and a B-line score of > 15 reflects hypervolemia in adults [79].

7.2.8 E-line

E-Lines are discrete laser-like vertical hyperechogenic ring-down artifacts [66], that arise **above** the pleural line, and move to the bottom without fading [1]. They are a sign of soft tissue emphysema [1].

7.2.9 S-line (Sunray Pattern)

S-lines are vertical ring-down artifacts starting from a consolidation in a recruitment maneuver [80, 81].

7.2.10 Z-Line

Z-Lines are ring-down artifacts [66] and correspond to Comet Tail Artifacts [63], that arise from the pleural line but with less echogenicity compared to the pleural line, unclear differentiation and fading after a short distance [69]. They erase the A-lines [63, 82]. Z-lines are not pathological.

7.2.11 Still Lung Point

The still lung point is a point in the parasternal transversal view in B- as well as in M-Mode between lung sliding and no lung sliding similar to the lung point; the still lung point is fixed and does not move during a breath cycle. It is a sign for pneumomediastinum [83].

7.2.12 Double Lung Point

The double lung point is a point where the lung is seemingly divided into one healthy (usually the upper anterior part) and one with coalescent B-lines (usually the inferior

Figure 7.8: Picture of a consolidation.

and dorsal parts) uni or bilaterally [39, 72, 84]. The double lung point is characteristic of transient tachypnoea of the newborn and is **not** seen in respiratory distress syndrome.

7.2.13 Consolidation

A consolidation refers to a region with tissue-like density [14, 42, 44, 50, 62, 85] (Figure 7.8). The term consolidation describes the image, not the cause. A consolidation can be seen in different pathologies (pneumonia, atelectasis, meconium aspiration syndrome, lung edema, lung hemorrhage, bronchopulmonary dysplasia, bronchiolitis, pulmonary embolism, contusion, tumor, drowning, lung infarction, CPAM) [38, 62, 75]. To differentiate lung from thymus, the liver or the spleen, or from another consolidation with of different origin (e.g.: tumor), the blood flow is visualized with color doppler. In lung tissue, the vessels have a tree-like pathway [63].

Shred Sign

The Shred Sign is a hyperechogenic (similar to the pleura) irregular line or border between aerated lung and consolidation [14, 44, 60].

Debris Sign

The Debris sign are small connected consolidations, small connected sandlike consolidations. It is a sign for development of bronchopulmonary dysplasia. If the Debris Sign is visible in a preterm infant, the OR for the development of a BPD is at 21.82 (95 % CI: 2.63-181.11) [86].

7.2.14 Aerobronchogram

Aerobronchogram is an image of air-filled bronchi within a consolidation [44].

Static aerobronchogram

A static aerobronchogram refers to air-filled bronchi within a consolidation where the bubbles show no movement and are static. A static aerobronchogram is visible in atelectasis and pneumonias.

Dynamic aerobronchogram

A dynamic aerobronchogram refers to air-filled bronchi in a consolidation where the bubbles move with every breath. A dynamic aerobronchogram is visible in pneumonia [87]. The Dynamic aerobronchogram excludes complete obstruction of the airways [63]. If a dynamic aerobronchogram is visible, this is suggestive of an inflammatory process in the lung tissue. The airways are open and the loss of aeration is caused by inflammation.

7.2.15 Fluidobronchogram

Liquid in the bronchi of a consolidation is called static fluidobronchogram [38]. It is visible in obstructive atelectasis or pneumonia [38], because the fluid stops air movement in the lung. If the fluid in the bronchi moves, it is called dynamic fluidobronchogram. Up until now, there is no correlation with that sign.

7.2.16 Fluid-color Sign

The fluid-color sign describes the movement in color doppler in an effusion. By this, an organized effusion can be differentiated from a liquid one [88].

7.2.17 Jellyfish Sign

In a pleural effusion the basal part of the lung might be consolidated and swim in a movement in synchrony with every breath, like a jellyfish. This is called jellyfish sign and is visible in large pleural effusions [89].

7.2.18 Sinusoid Sign

When examined on the M-mode a sinusoid pattern becomes visible with a hyperechogenic sinusoidal line above the effusion [89]. This sign is specific for a pleural effusion [44, 61, 89].

7.2.19 Mirrored Ribs

In pneumothorax, the high difference in acoustic impedance between the *Pleura parietalis* and air in the pleural space causes increased mirroring and reverberation. If the ribs are

not ossified and visible as black round structures, they are seen as long line reverberation artifacts below the pleural line multiple times [90].

7.2.20 Plankton Sign

The plankton sign describes slowly moving echogenic particles similar to plankton in pleural effusion. The movement is in sync with breathing or the heart beat [89].

7.2.21 Sunray Pattern (S-line)

The sunray or s-pattern describes vertical ring-down artifacts starting from a consolidation in a recruitment maneuver [80, 81].

7.3 BLUE Protocol - D. Lichtenstein [1]

The BLUE protocol (see figure 7.9) allows fast assessment in critically ill patients. It was developed by D. Lichtenstein. In contrast to conventional lung ultrasound it uses pattern recognition called profiles. The profiles are several pathologic consistent presentations for underlying pathologies and therefore allow fast assessment and communication. [1]

Profiles in the Blue-protocol

A-profile A-profile describes anterior A-lines and a maximum of 2 B-lines per intercostal space [1]. Also known as A-pattern [36], but A-profile is the recommended term.

A'-profile A'-profile describes anterior A-lines without lung sliding [1].

B-profile B-profile describes 3 or more B-lines per intercostal space (lung rockets) in anterior areas [1]. This is also described as B-pattern [36], but B-profile is recommended.

B'-profile B'-profile is a B-profile without lung sliding. [1]

A/B-profile A/B-profile describes a unilateral B-profile. [1]

C-profile C-profile describes anterior consolidations. [1]

Figure 7.9: Flowchart BLUE protocol - Lichtenstein et al. [1]

7.4 Semiquantitative Assessment

7.4.1 Score

Neonates For assessment of lung ultrasound score (LUS-scores, see Table 7.1) the scoring value of each scanned area in the transthoracic or transabdominal view is added to get the overall score [50, 91, 92]. The first score was proposed by Via et al. in 2012 [50].

The inter-observer reliability is high: kappa 0.79-0.83 [93] and the score can be performed during transport with high accuracy [94].

The score correlates with molecular and cellular inflammation [95], with interleukin-6 [96], histologic changes and interpulmonary shunts in neonatal acute respiratory distress syndrome (nARDS) [58], the postnatal fluid reabsorption [74, 97], increased lung fluids [97], oxygenation-index in neonates [92, 98, 99, 100, 101, 102] and children [20], the need for surfactant [92, 101, 102, 103, 104] and the silverman-score [100] in RDS [99], with respiratory system compliance [105] the need for ventilation in neonates [102, 103, 106], the venous pH and venous pCO₂ in neonates [107], the need for respiratory support [103] the need for oxygen and longer duration of stay in acute bronchiolitis [108, 109]. In an animal model it could be shown, that lung ultrasound score detected large changes in total and regional lung volumen in real time and correctly identified opening and closing pressures [110]. The score decreases in neonates over 32 weeks gestational age with respiratory distress, when nCPAP is applied [111].

Furthermore, the score was used to predict successful extubation [112, 113, 114], see Chapter 10.2.5.

Children In children, the score at first assessment, regardless if the patient presented with wheezing, bronchiolitis, pneumonia or asthma, was predictive of severity as defined by the need of escalated care with HFNC, NIV or mechanical ventilation [115]. However, whether it can be used to estimate additional vascular lung water, especially at low thresholds remains unclear up to date [116].

Normal values are displayed in Table 7.2.

The inherent problems with a semiquantitative score are regularly discussed [117], yet the published correlations remain unchanged.

In preterm and term infants, the score is dependent on positioning and gravity [118, 119]. After six hours of prone positioning in RDS, nARDS and developing BPD, the score decreases significantly. Additionally, the consolidations shift from dorsal in the supine position to ventral in the prone position [119].

Adaptions of the lung ultrasound score

In 2020, Girona-Alarcón [120] published an adaption for children after cardiac surgery, see Table 7.1.

In 2021, Szymański et al. [121] proposed an adaption expanding the score by one additional parameter, see Table 7.1. This score is the second most frequently used [121,122].

In 2022, Rodriguez-Gonzalez et al. proposed an extended score weighting consolidations and their sizes higher [123]. In the same year Jiang et al. [124] published an alternative score with 14 regions by adding the basal areas using abdominal views to the 12-region method. This score correlated with the need for surfactant and need for ventilation in 88 neonates [124]. A very similar approach was used by Sun et al., the basal areas were added to the 6-region method. This score is associated with BPD, increased oxygen requirements and duration of stay [125]. In contrast, Kasniya et al. [77] focused on quantifying B-lines and called it pulmonary edema severity score. This score improved significantly with diuretic therapy in patients with bronchopulmonary dysplasia [77].

In 2023, Zong et al. used the score published by Brat et al. [92] and extended it with a 4 for extended consolidations [126]. Pierro et al. used a classification for different pathologies and called it score [127] and Wang et al. used a different score based on the number of B-lines to observe BPD development [128].

In 2024 Loi et al. further adapted the score from 6 to 10 views, five on each side (two anterior, one lateral, two posterior) [119,129] and named this score extended lung ultrasound score (eLUS) [119].

In contrast to most adaptions, Sefic et al. proposed a different approach, similar to Lichtenstein, with profiles: profile 1 ist a normal lung, profile 2 are coalescent B lines and profile 3 are coalescent B-lines without spared areas, the classification a is added if consolidations are present [130]. While being easy to apply, this system was only validated in RDS and correlated with chest-X-ray, not with need for surfactant or oxygen requirement [130].

Although different adaptions and expansions were published and proposed, lung ultrasound score published by Brat et al. in 2015 [92] is considered the current standard.

Table 7.1: LUS-Score by Brat et al. [92], Taveira et al. [91] and Perri et al. [104] modified by Rodriguez-Gonzalez et al. [123], Jiang et al. [124], Girona-Alarcón et al. [120] and Szymański et al. [121], Pierro et al. [127], Zong et al. [126], Sefic et al. [130], Wang et al. [128] and Kasniya et al. [77].

Score	Description
Brat et al. (current standard) [92]	
0	Normal pleural line with horizontal A-lines
1	3 or more B-lines per intercostal space and a regular thin pleural line

- 2 Coalescent B-lines and a thick pleural line with or without small consolidations
- 3 Thick irregular pleural line with consolidations

Szymański et al. [121]

- 0 Normal pleural line with horizontal reverberations of the a-lines (A-profile)
- 1 3 or more B-Lines per intercostal space and a regular thin pleural line (B-profile)
- 2 Coalescent B-lines and a thick pleural line; white lung
- 3 White lung with fluid alveologram and no consolidations (debris sign)
- 4 A thick irregular pleural line with consolidations

Rodriguez-Gonzalez et al. [123]

- 0 2 or less B-lines per intercostal space
- 1 3 or more B-Lines per intercostal space or one intercostal space with coalescent B-lines
- 2 2 or more intercostal spaces with coalescent B-lines
- 3 Consolidations
- +0 No consolidations
- +1 1 consolidation <1 cm
- +2 1 >1 cm or more small consolidations

Jiang et al. [124]

- 0 2 or less B-lines per intercostal space
- 1 3 or more B-lines per intercostal space
- 2 Partly coalescent B-lines
- 3 Coalescent B-Lines
- 4 Irregular pleural line with consolidations <1 cm
- 5 Irregular pleural line with consolidations >1 cm

LUCAS - Girona-Alarcón et al. [120]

- 0 A-lines without B-lines
- 1 2 or less B-lines per intercostal space
- 2 3-7 B-lines per intercostal space
- 3 Coalescent B-lines or >7 B-lines per intercostal space
- 4 Pleural effusion

LUCAS - scoring in 6 regions [120]

- 0-5 Normal
- 6-9 Mild lung edema
- 10-14 Moderate lung edema
- >14 Severe lung edema

Pierro et al. [127]

- 0 A-Pattern: A-lines and 0-2 B-lines
- 1 B1-Pattern: 3 or more B-lines

- 2 Double lung point
- 3 B2 Pattern: coalescent B-lines
- 4 White lung and pleural line abnormalities or ground-glass opacity or snowflake sign
- 5 Irregular atelectasis: pulmonary consolidations

Zong et al. [126]

- 0 presence of under 3 well-spaced B-lines
- 1 presence of 3 or more well-spaced B-lines
- 2 B-lines are difficult to count, or partially coalescent
- 3 fully coalescent B-Lines, with or without minor consolidations limited to the subpleural space
- 4 extended consolidations

Sefic et al. [130]

- 1 coalescent B lines without spared areas of lungs
- 1a Profile 1 with consolidations
- 2 coalescent B-lines
- 2a Profile 2 with consolidations
- 3 A-lines

Wang et al. [128]

- 0 A-lines and maximum 3 B-lines
- 1 4-6 B-lines
- 2 over 6 B-lines
- 3 B-lines and no A-lines

Pulmonary Severity Score by Kasniya et al. [77]

- 0 0-5 B-lines in 3 intercostal spaces
 - 1 6-10 B-lines in 3 intercostal spaces
 - 2 11-15 B-lines in 3 intercostal spaces
 - 3 16-20 B-lines in 3 intercostal spaces
 - 4 under 3 coalescent B-lines in 3 intercostal spaces
 - 5 coalescent B-lines in 3 intercostal spaces
-

Development of Lung Ultrasound Score over Time

The lung ultrasound score is not influenced by clinical chorioamnionitis [131]. After birth, the lung score develops differently depending on the gestational age at birth [132]: In preterm infants born at a gestational age of 23-27 weeks the score increased until the 5th week of life, but a significant difference remains between patients developing a bronchopulmonary dysplasia and others on the 3rd day after birth, after 1 week and after 3 weeks of life. In preterm infants born at a gestational age of 28-32 weeks, the lung ultrasound score decreases rapidly within the first days after birth and

Table 7.2: LUS-Score normal values for term neonates [74] for the score published by Brat et al. [92] OS, observational study.

Healthy term neonates					
Age	Regions	Median (Quartile)	n (mean gestational age)	Type	Reference
<3 h	12	8 (7-11)	66 (38.75)	OS	[74]
6 h	12	2 (0-4)	66 (38.75)	OS	[74]
24 h	12	1 (0-2)	66 (38.75)	OS	[74]

there is a significant difference between patients developing BPD and others between the 3rd day after birth and the 7th week of life. [132]. In neonates born after 35 weeks gestation, the conventional lung ultrasound score (anterior and lateral) and extended (anterior, lateral and posterior) remain equal in the first 2 h of life improving within the first 8 h showing no statistical significance between 8 h and 24 h.

stay the same for the first 2 h [129] and the score improves within the first 8 h with no statistical significance between 8 h and 48 h [129].

After birth, the lung ultrasound score decreases in all healthy neonates, but is higher in preterm infants with BPD and equalizes after 8 months [133].

Score and Different Diseases

The lung ultrasound score can be used to predict the need for surfactant or ventilation in respiratory distress syndrome and the development of a bronchopulmonary dysplasia. In most studies, two anterior and one lateral view were performed on the right and on the left side. Loi et al. proposed that the lung ultrasound score should be divided by the gestational age to achieve higher accuracy [100]. This could not be reproduced in a systematic review with meta analysis [134].

Chapter 8.2.5 represents a detailed list of possibilities to predict bronchopulmonary dysplasia and Chapter 8.2.26 a detailed list for the prediction of need for surfactant or ventilation in RDS.

The score (extended by a value of 4 for presence of herniated viscera) improves in neonates with congenital diaphragmatic hernia after surgery [135].

Score and Patent Ductus Arteriosus Botalli

The lung ultrasound correlates with the presence [97] and the diameter of the PDA [136, 137], the duration of hospital admission [136] as well as the LA/AO ratio [137]. The amount of pulmonary flooding in a hemodynamically significant PDA can be quantified using the lung ultrasound score [136]. A score >9 predicts a PDA with a sensitivity of 93.75 % and a specificity of 50.95 % [137]. This means, that with a score

of ≤ 9 a PDA is unlikely. With a score >9 a PDA but also other pathologies are present. Hence the lung ultrasound score can only be seen as a screening parameter rather than a diagnostic test.

Zong et al. used a 12-view approach and extended the Brat-Score by a 4 for extended consolidations; in this score a cut-off of 33 on the fourth day after birth had a high accuracy with a specificity of 89 % and a sensitivity of 87 % for PDA [126]. Zong et al. used the same score to predict PDA in preterm infants born at 25 weeks gestational age or earlier with a cut-off of 36 on the 14th day after birth with a sensitivity of 96 % and a specificity of 86 % [138].

The lung ultrasound score can be used to detect increased lung fluids due to a PDA [97]. After ligation of PDA, it takes 12 h until the score decreases [139].

Score and Extracorporeal Membrane Oxygenation

A lack of improvement of lung ultrasound score during weaning of ECMO is associated with increased mortality [20].

Score and Aeration

The score correlates with aeration in RDS [99] but not with lung volume in chest-X-ray [140].

7.5 Atelectasis Depth

Another semiquantitative approach is measuring the depth of atelectasis. This did not correspond with global atelectasis [140].

7.6 Diaphragm

7.6.1 Diaphragm Excursion

The diaphragmatic excursion allows interpretation of work of breathing and tidal volume. Especially a unilateral or paradox movement can be suggestive of diaphragmatic nerve palsy. A linear probe is used to measure the excursion in subcostal transversal view orthogonal to the pleura in M-mode by measuring the difference between in- and expiration.

Table 7.3: Physiologic values for diaphragmatic shortening fraction (DSF), minimal (TIT) and maximal (TET) thickness of diaphragm in the first 24 h in term- (T) and preterm infants (PT) [141].

Parameter	T	PT
Right		
TIT (mm)	2.6 (2.2-3.2)	1.6 (1.5-1.9)
TET (mm)	1.9 (1.6-2.4)	1.2 (1.1-1.4)
DSF (%)	24 (15-37)	33 (24-46)
Left		
TIT (mm)	2.6 (1.9-3.2)	1.6 (1.3-2.1)
TET (mm)	1.9 (1.6-2.4)	1.2 (1.1-1.6)
DSF (%)	32 (15-40)	32 (26-39)

7.6.2 Diaphragmatic Shortening Fraction by Alonso et al [141].

The transducer is placed between anterior and posterior axillary line between 8th and 9th rib orthogonal to the pleura (coronar/vertical). There are two echogenic lines, the one closer to the transducer is the pleura parietalis and the other one is the peritoneum. The diaphragm is the hypoechogenic structure between those two. In M-Mode, the minimal (TET) and the maximal thickness (TIT) during a breathing cycle are measured three times with the following formula:

$$DSF(\%) = \frac{TIT - TET}{TET} \times 100$$

The TIT and the TET are higher in term neonates compared to preterm neonates, but the DSF is equal. Physiologic values in the first 24 h are visible in Table 7.3.

Diaphragmatic shortening fraction performed between the 9th and 10th rib orthogonal to the pleura (coronar/vertical) in the mid axillary line and diaphragmatic excursion (highest peak from baseline) calculated as an average from at least three respiratory cycles showed high inter-observer agreement for DSF with 0.86 (95 % CI: 0.84-0.87) and DE with 0.93 (95 % CI: 0.91-0.94). Diaphragmatic excursion was higher in preterm infants ventilated with NIV-NAVA compared to NIPPV [142]. But DSF was not significantly different in preterm infants with extubation failure [122].

Chapter 8

Diagnostic Findings in Lung Ultrasound (alphabetic)

8.1 Physiological Findings

- Smooth straight pleural line [14, 50, 127]
- Smooth straight A-lines [14, 50, 127]
- 0-2 B-lines per intercostal space [14, 127]. Especially in the first days after birth, more B-lines are physiologic [73, 127] but the number decreases in the first 24 h [63, 73] and vanish before the third day after birth [63].
- Lung sliding [14]
- Seashore sign [14]
- In neonates: lung pulse

8.2 Pathological Findings in Lung Ultrasound

Lung ultrasound is based on the interpretation of artifacts. Artifacts can be physiological or pathological. The direct visualisation of tissue-like structures or tissue itself is always pathological. A well aerated lung produces exclusively artifacts.

Only pathologies with a connection to the pleura are visible in lung ultrasound. Therefore, central consolidations, central pneumonias, or cPAMs or lung sequestrs are not detected. The following list ist alphabetical.

8.2.1 Alveolar Pneumonia

The ESPNIC POCUS guidelines state, that lung ultrasound is useful in the detection of pneumonia [143]. Lung ultrasound is effective in the diagnosis of pneumonia with a sensitivity of 96 % (95 % CI: 94-97 %) and a specificity of 93 % (95 % CI: 90-96 %) in a systematic review with meta-analysis [144].

In a prospective observational study lung ultrasound had a sensitivity of 97.5 % and a specificity of 95 % [145].

However, lung ultrasound can not differentiate between different pathogens [146, 147]. Furthermore, lung ultrasound was used as gold standard in a large case-control study on the effectiveness of the 10-valent pneumococcal conjugate vaccine on pediatric pneumonia [148] and in the Household Air Pollution Intervention Network Trial [149]. Lung ultrasound can be used to diagnose early-onset round pneumonia [150].

The following signs are suggestive of pneumonia in patients with the corresponding clinical picture.

- Consolidation (hepatization) with dynamic aerobronchogram (tree-like or linear) and irregular borders, the shred sign [14, 59, 151, 152, 153, 154, 155]. The presence of a dynamic aerobronchogram suggests an inflammatory process.
- Thick, rough pleural line with coarse areas, disruptions and absence of the pleural line [14, 151, 152]
- Lung edema / interstitial syndrome, the presence of three or more B-lines per intercostal space up to a white lung [14, 50, 59, 151, 152].
- Lung pulse in affected area [151, 153]
- Pleural effusion locally or basally [14, 154]

Ventilator Associated Pneumonia

Lung ultrasound can be used to detect ventilator associated pneumonia (VAP). A multiparameter score developed by Tusor et al. [154] includes lung ultrasound and achieves a high accuracy (sensitivity: 94-94 %, specificity: 67-83 %, AUC 0.91-0.97). Lung ultrasound (AUC 0.98) is superior in the diagnosis of VAP compared to chest-X-ray if the clinical diagnosis is used as gold standard [156]. The following signs were used:

- Consolidation [146] (>0.5 cm [154]) with aerobronchogram [146, 154, 156]: Sen: 96.5 %; Spe: 100 % [156]
- Interstitial syndrome: Sen: 98.3 %; Spe: 28.6 % [124]
- Pleural effusion [154, 156]: Sen: 10.4 %; Spe: 28.6 % [124]

- Abnormal pleural line [146, 156]: Sen: 99.1 %; Spe: 14.3 % [156]
- Lung pulse [156]: Sen: 13 %; Spe: 100 % [156]

Differentiation between bacterial and viral pneumonia

In 2022, Omran et al. showed in children that consolidations >1 cm with air bronchogram are statistically significantly associated with bacterial pneumonias [155] but the signs are the same [151].

8.2.2 Alveolar capillary dysplasia with malalignment of the pulmonary veins

- Thickened pleural line [157].
- Dense and prominent B-lines [157]

8.2.3 Atelectasis (Neonatal Pulmonary Atelectasis)

Lung ultrasound has a very high accuracy for neonatal pulmonary atelectasis with a sensitivity of 100 % and a specificity of 100 % [85].

In a prospective observational study lung ultrasound had a sensitivity of 100 % and a specificity of 97.8 % [145].

- Areal consolidation with smooth borders to other lung-structures (specificity 100 %) [14, 50, 85, 145]
- Absence of lung sliding in affected area [14, 61, 85]
- **Possible:** Presence of aerobronchogram [85]; a dynamic aerobronchogram is suggestive of inflammatory processes; DD: pneumonia.
- **Possible, in neonates not valid:** lung pulse [85] in complete atelectasis [14, 39, 152]
- **Possible:** In color doppler, blood flow is visible [14]

In a case report, Liu et al. reported a successful treatment of an atelectasis using bronchoalveolar lavage until the signs in lung ultrasound were no longer visible [158].

Radiologic Classification

Atelectasis can be divided into radiologic classifications. Focal type atelectasis show corresponding findings in chest-X-ray, whereas no such can be seen in an occult lung atelectasis.

Focal Type Atelectasis Neonatal Pulmonary Atelectasis with corresponding finding in chest X-ray.

- Consolidation with clear border [85]
- **Possible:** aerobronchogram [85]

Occult Lung Atelectasis Neonatal Pulmonary Atelectasis without corresponding finding in chest X-ray.

- Small consolidation with punctual aerobronchogram [85].
- Abnormal pleural line and absence of A-lines in affected area [85].
- Normal pleural line, A-lines und lung sliding in unaffected areas [85].

Pathognomonic Classification

Atelectases can be divided into atelectasis caused by compression or atelectasis caused by obstruction.

Atelectasis caused by compression

- Central static aerobronchogram
- Pleural effusion

Atelectasis caused by obstruction

- Initial static aerobronchogram [87].

8.2.4 Bronchial Atresia

- Isolated consolidation with aerobronchogram [159]

8.2.5 Bronchopulmonary Dysplasia

Lung ultrasound can be used as an early predictor of BPD [160, 161].

Cave: one third of patients with signs of bronchopulmonary dysplasia (BPD) in lung ultrasound have a different diagnosis: pneumonia, atelectasis or interstitial syndrome [162].

- Bilateral affection of the pleura and lung [40, 163]

- Inhomogenic image of an irregular pleura with small consolidations [40, 163, 164] next to areas with A-lines.
- 2 or more B-lines per intercostal space up to a white lung [40, 163]
- Increased echogenicity in the lungbases in the transabdominal views [163, 165]
- Debris sign [86]
- Gravity independent changes of the lung [78].

Overdistension

In severe hyperinflation the lung sliding might vanish [166]. But there is no valid sign for overdistension.

Prediction of Bronchopulmonary Dysplasia

A systematic review reported that lung ultrasound is able to predict the development of BPD in preterm infants born <32 weeks gestational age and that an extended score divided by gestational age does not improve accuracy [134]. The accuracy of the lung ultrasound score is superior to NT-proBNP [93].

Different possibilities to predict the development of BPD using lung ultrasound are visible in Table 8.1.

Preterm infants born between 23 to 27 weeks gestation In preterm infants born between 23-27 weeks gestation, higher scoring levels can be seen until the 5th week after birth, but there is still a significant difference between patients developing BPD and others on day 3, after the first week of life and after the third week of life [132, 167].

Preterm infants born between 28 to 32 weeks gestation In preterm infants born in 28-32 weeks gestation, the lung ultrasound score decreases rapidly within the first days after birth [132, 167] and shows a significant difference between patients developing BPD and others in the first three weeks of life [132, 167] and 7th week of life [132]. The best diagnostic accuracy for prognostic bronchopulmonary dysplasia was achieved in preterm infants born under <31 weeks gestation on day 7 and 14. [100] [168].

Most studies used three views per side: two anterior and one lateral view. In 2021, Loi et al. showed no higher accuracy in predicting BPD by using an additional posterior scan in preterm infants <31 weeks gestation [100]. In contrast Liu et al. found a significantly better prognosis using posterior views as well [168].

Woods et al. stated in an observational study, that lung ultrasound was able to predict the development of BPD in preterm infants born <28 weeks gestation, but the main

factor of prediction was gestational age and not the lung ultrasound score [169]. Lung ultrasound enables to monitor the development of this chronic disease and start therapy accordingly (e.g. vitamin A injections or in future stem cell therapy) [170]. If diuretics are started, the number of B-lines decrease and oxygenation improves [77, 171].

Table 8.1: Different criteria (echogenicity of diaphragm (Di), Score (Number of views and localisation anterior and lateral (a+l) or anterior, lateral and posterior (a+l+p)) in lung ultrasound and the development of bronchopulmonary dysplasia (BPD) at a time point (day (d) or week of life (w)) with corresponding sensitivity (Sen), Specificity (Spe), negative predictive value (NPV) and positive predictive value (PPV) and the characteristics of the analysed patients (number and mean/median gestational age) and studies (observational study (OS), retrospective study (RS)) and the references.

Criteria (regions)	d/w	BPD definition	Sen (%)	Spe (%)	NPV (%)	PPV (%)	n (mean/median gestational age)	Type	Reference
23-27 weeks gestational age									
LUS Score >5 (6, a+l)	3 d	28d O ₂ /36 W & CPAP/O ₂	76.2	62.1	59.3	78.3	43	OS	[167]
LUS Score >5 (6, a+l)	7 d	28d O ₂ /36 W & CPAP/O ₂	71.4	73.6	66.2	78.0	43	OS	[167]
LUS Score >4 (6, a+l)	14 d	28d O ₂ /36 W & CPAP/O ₂	85.7	67.8	65.9	86.8	43	OS	[167]
LUS Score >5 (6, a+l)	21 d	28d O ₂ /36 W & CPAP/O ₂	76.2	72.4	66.7	80.8	43	OS	[167]
28-32 weeks gestational age									
LUS Score >5 (6, a+l)	3 d	28d O ₂ /36 W & CPAP/O ₂	76.7	64.9	46.0	87.7	107	OS	[167]
LUS Score >5 (6, a+l)	7 d	28d O ₂ /36 W & CPAP/O ₂	60.0	77.9	51.4	83.3	107	OS	[167]
LUS Score >4 (6, a+l)	14 d	28d O ₂ /36 W & CPAP/O ₂	70.0	75.3	52.5	86.6	107	OS	[167]
LUS Score >4 (6, a+l)	21 d	28d O ₂ /36 W & CPAP/O ₂	80.0	68.8	50.0	89.8	107	OS	[167]
All gestational ages									
LUS Score >6 (6)	1 d	28d O ₂ /36 W & CPAP/O ₂	80	71.4	90.9	50	64 (27.4; 29.5 W)	OS	[172]
LUS Score >20 (12)	1 d	36 W & CPAP/O ₂	18.6	95.8	66	72.7	130 (29.2 W)	OS	[168]
LUS Score >9 (6, a+l)	1 d	28d O ₂ /36 W & CPAP/O ₂	75.5	70.4	48.8	88.5	64 (30.7)	OS	[173]
LUS Score >16 (12)	2 d	36 W & CPAP/O ₂	36	86.3	62.1	62.1	130 (29.2 W)	OS	[168]
LUS Score >9 (6, a+l)	2 d	28d O ₂ /36 W & CPAP/O ₂	75.5	70.4	48.8	88.5	64 (30.7)	OS	[173]
LUS Score >18 (12)	3 d	36 W & CPAP/O ₂	38	88.8	67.9	69.6	130 (29.2 W)	OS	[168]
LUS Score >10 (6)	3 d	36 W & CPAP/O ₂	89	80	92	92	152 (25.8 W)	OS	[174]
LUS Score >9 (6, a+l)	3 d	28d O ₂ /36 W & CPAP/O ₂	75.5	70.4	48.8	88.5	64 (30.7)	OS	[173]
LUS Score >13 (12)	6 d	36 W & CPAP/O ₂	46	87.5	69.7	72.2	130 (29.2 W)	OS	[168]
LUS Score >8 (8)	7 d	28d O ₂ /36 W & CPAP/O ₂	90	81			42 (29.5; 27 W)	OS	[175]
LUS Score >8 (6, a+l)	7 d	28d O ₂ /36 W & CPAP/O ₂	70	79			298 (26; 29 W)	OS	[176]
LUS Score >5 (8)	7 d	28d O ₂ /36 W & CPAP/O ₂	90	81			42 (29.5; 27 W)	OS	[175]
LUS Score >8 (8)	7 d	36 W & CPAP/O ₂	93	91			42 (29.5; 27 W)	OS	[175]
$\frac{LUS_{Score}}{GA} >0.23$ (6, a+l)	7 d	36 W & CPAP/O ₂	71	74	54	73	147 (27.1 W)	OS	[100]
LUS Score >10 (6)	7 d	36 W & CPAP/O ₂	89	90	87	92	152 (25.8 W)	OS	[174]
Echogenität Zw									
LUS Score >11 (12)	9 d	28 d & abnormales C/P	100	50	100	43	59 (29.27 W)	OS	[165]
LUS Score >11 (12)	9 d	36 W & CPAP/O ₂	64	85	72.7	79.1	130 (29.2 W)	OS	[168]
LUS Score >8 (12)	12 d	36 W & CPAP/O ₂	74	84.6	75.5	83.5	130 (29.2 W)	OS	[168]
$\frac{LUS_{Score}}{GA} >0.31$ (6, a+l)	14 d	36 W & CPAP/O ₂	66	81	77	71	147 (27.1 W)	OS	[100]
LUS Score >5 (6)	2. LW	28d O ₂ /36 W & CPAP/O ₂	73.7	100	78.3	100	64 (27.4; 29.5 W)	OS	[172]
LUS Score >10 (6)	7 d	36 W & CPAP/O ₂	77	92	88	84	152 (25.8 W)	OS	[174]
LUS Score >8 (12)	12 d	36 W & CPAP/O ₂	72	82.3	72	82.3	130 (29.2 W)	OS	[168]
Echogenität Zw									
LUS Score >6 (8)	18 d	28 d & O ₂	100	95.2			105 (29.1; 32.7 W)	OS	[177]
LUS Score >6 (8)	2-8. LW	36 W & CPAP/O ₂	76	97	88	97	27 (26; 28 W)	RS	[178]
LUS Score >4 (8)	28 d	28d O ₂ /36 W & CPAP/O ₂	95	86			42 (29.5; 27 W)	OS	[175]
LUS Score >6 (8)	28 d	36 W & CPAP/O ₂	85	82			42 (29.5; 27 W)	OS	[175]
LUS Score >7 (6, a+l+p)	28 d	36 W & CPAP/O ₂	85	92	84	93	87 (29.4 SSW)	OS	[179]

8.2.6 Bronchiolitis

The ESPNIC POCUS guidelines state that lung ultrasound is helpful to uncover bronchiolitis but not to diagnose its cause [143]. In a case series, Walsh et al. could show that lung ultrasound was able to detect children with bronchiolitis faster compared to auscultation [180]. The lung ultrasound findings in bronchiolitis are associated with oxygen requirements and the severity of the disease [96, 181].

A systematic review concluded, that lung ultrasound could have a role in diagnosing bronchiolitis and predicting the need of PICU admission, hospital stay and respiratory support [182].

- Thick, rough pleural line [59, 143]
- 2 or more B-lines per intercostal space [59, 75, 143, 181, 183]
The number of B-lines correlates to the severity of the disease and the oxygen requirements [181, 183].
- **Possible:** Consolidations of different sizes [59, 143, 181] especially paravertebral and posterior [181] but smaller in size compared to pneumonias (<1 cm). The area of consolidation correlates with the severity of the disease and the oxygen requirement [181].

Score and Bronchiolitis

The lung ultrasound score by Brat et al. [92] correlates with oxygen requirement, severity of the disease and length of stay [108, 109]. A score >6 predicts the necessity of PICU admission with a sensitivity of 90.9% and a specificity of 88.89% [184].

An adapted score with greater weighing consolidations more could predict with a cut-off at 10 the necessity of ventilation with a sensitivity of 44%, and a specificity of 88%, a positive predictive value of 64% and a negative predictive value of 77% [123]. The score correlates with the severity of the disease and can be used as prognostic tool [183].

COVID-19

The signs visible in SARS-CoV-2 infections (COVID-19) are the same seen in any viral bronchiolitis [185, 186, 187]. Lung ultrasound was able to detect the signs of COVID-19 in neonates [96, 186, 187], especially in patients without clinical symptoms [188]. Furthermore, lung ultrasound is very useful in the assessment in the outpatient setting. A systematic review identified the following signs:

- Absence of A-lines [189, 190]

- Increased B-lines [189, 190]
- Thick, disrupted pleural line [189]
- Bilateral consolidations especially in inferior areas. [189]

Pediatric Patients Pediatric patients show the same signs for COVID-19 [190].

8.2.7 Congenital Diaphragmatic Hernia

Lung ultrasound can be used to diagnose and exclude a congenital diaphragmatic hernia (CDH) [8]. Although intrathoracic parenchymatic organs are typical for CDH, there are differential diagnosis that might look similar, e.g. in one case with CDH diagnosed by chest-X-ray, lung ultrasound was able to identify multiple lung cysts caused by *S. aureus* infection [8].

- Absence of diaphragm [191] or visible discontinuation of hyperechogenic line seen in transabdominal view [192]
- Absence of pleural line in affected area [191, 192]
- Absence of A-lines in affected area [192]
- Consolidations in bordering areas [192]
- Paradox movement of the abdominal organs (abdominal view)
- Intrathoracic parenchymatic organs (liver, spleen) [191, 192]
or
Presence of a multilayered area with hyperechogenic content (intrathoracic intestines) [191, 192]
- **Possible:** Peristalsis in affected area [192]

Postoperative Care

Lung ultrasound is a valuable tool for evaluating the progressive re-aeration of the lung and pleural effusion following surgical correction in CDH patients. It demonstrates the ability to diagnose common postoperative complications [193].

8.2.8 Congenital pulmonary airway malformation (CPAM)

Lung ultrasound can be used to detect a cystic malformation of the lung [17, 194, 195, 196, 197]

- One or more hypoechogenic cystic lesions [17, 25, 194, 197]
- Consolidation in affected area [17, 25, 194, 197]
- Absence of pleural line in affected area [17, 25, 194]
- No abnormal feeding vessel [194, 196]

8.2.9 Contusion

A contusion can be seen in ultrasound [38].

- Consolidation [38, 50]
- Increased number of B-lines [50]

8.2.10 Pulmonary Infarction

Infarction of the lung is visible as consolidation without normal perfusion [44].

8.2.11 Interstitial lung disease

Childhood interstitial lung disease is a heterogenous group of respiratory disorders affecting the lung tissue, with significant morbidity and mortality.

- 3 or more B-lines [198].
- Fragmented pleural line [198].

8.2.12 Foreign Body Aspiration

Although over 77% of patients with foreign body aspiration have abnormal lung ultrasound signs, there is no specific constellation of signs [199]: coalescent B-lines, consolidations as well as stratosphere sign is reported [199]. Depending on the affected segment, signs of atelectasis and, later, pneumonia are expected.

8.2.13 Hypervolemia

In infants and children receiving renal replacement therapy, hypervolemia can be quantified by using lung ultrasound and the signs for interstitial and alveolar syndrome [70]. A minimum of 8-12 B-lines were observed in patients with moderate to severe fluid overload [70].

8.2.14 Lung Edema

The ESPNIC POCUS guidelines state that lung ultrasound is helpful in the detection of lung edema [143]. Lung ultrasound can not differentiate between cardiogenic and non-cardiogenic lung edema [143]. Development of lung edema is a gradual process. 2 or less B-lines per intercostal space are represent a physiological fluid amount of the interstitium an the interlobal space. Increasing interstitial fluid leads to an increasing number of B-lines as well leading to an interstitial syndrome. Excess fluid in the interstitial compartment moves to the alveolar space causing consolidations and a rough thickened pleural line (alveolar syndrome) [200]. A further fluid increase leads to larger consolidations with an aerobronchogram [200] and pleural effusion. However, lung ultrasound cannot identify the cause of the excessive fluid.

Interstitial Syndrome

- 3 or more B-Lines per intercostal space in every area (e.g. bei PDA, VSD) [38, 39, 70, 136, 152, 201]
- **Or:** two or more intercostal spaces with coalescent B-lines [14].

Severe Interstitial Syndrome

- Glass rockets: 5-12 B-lines per intercostal space [75]
- **Or:** White lung [14]

Alveolar Syndrome

- Two or more bordering intercostal spaces with coalescent B-lines [14, 75]
- Rough, thickened pleural line

8.2.15 Meconium Aspiration Syndrome

The ESPNIC POCUS guidelines state that lung ultrasound is helpful in the detection of meconium aspiration syndrome [143].

In a prospective observational study, lung ultrasound had a sensitivity of 92.3 % and a specificity of 100 % [145].

- Heterogenous changes in both lungs [14, 39, 202, 203]
- Consolidations (hepatization) with aerobronchogram and irregular borders [14, 39, 145, 202, 203]
- B-lines and consolidations with spared areas inbetween [14, 39, 202, 203]

In a case report, Liu et al. describe the successful therapy of meconium aspiration syndrome by performing bronchoalveolar lavage until the signs vanished in lung ultrasound [158].

8.2.16 Neonatal Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome

The ESPNIC POCUS guidelines state, that lung ultrasound is helpful in the semi-quantitative assessment of aeration in the management of neonatal acute respiratory distress syndrome (nARDS) [143]. This recommendation is consistent with published animal-studies [58].

- Bilateral diffuse areas with consolidations and an increased number of B-lines [143]
- Abnormal (thickened, rough) pleural line [143]
- Pleural effusion [143]

8.2.17 Neonatal Bile Acid Pneumonia

There are no specific features in neonatal bile acid pneumonia [204]. It is a mild disorder in the first hours after birth and progresses into RDS [204].

8.2.18 Pediatric Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome

Desanti et al. showed that a blinded lung ultrasound was able to detect the underlying pathology behind pediatric acute respiratory distress syndrome (pARDS) in 56 % of cases [205].

Figure 8.1: Picture of a pleural effusion.

8.2.19 Pleural Effusion

The ESPNIC POCUS guidelines state, that lung ultrasound is helpful in detecting pleural effusion [143]. Ultrasound guided punctures show a decrease in the probability of complications [143].

Pleural effusion presents as an anechoic or echogenic area between the parietal and pulmonary pleura (Figure 8.1) [25]. Only the placement of a chest tube confirms the diagnosis [89].

- Jellyfish sign [89]
- Sinusoid sign in M-mode [38, 89]
- Quad sign: Fluid between pulmonary and parietal pleura [44].

Transudate

- Always anechoic [89]

Exsudate

Visible in hemorrhage, fibrinic or putride exsudation.

- Anechoic, echogenic or with particles (plankton sign, Chapter 7.2.20) or septa [38, 89].

Purulent effusion

- Echogenic [89]
- **Possible:** fine echogenic septae [89].
- **Possible:** multiple echogenic alveoli similar to honeycomb [38, 89].

- **Possible:** Plankton sign (Chapter 7.2.20): slowly swimming echogenic particles similar to plankton. The movement is synchron to breathing or the heart beat [89].
- **Possible:** In pneumococcal disease, the pleural effusion has an echogenic border [89].

Hemothorax

- Echogenic with plankton sign [89].

8.2.20 Pneumomediastinum

Pneumomediastinum can be diagnosed using lung ultrasound.

- Still Lung Point [83]
- Thickend curved line below the thymus [63, 206]
- Gap Sign: no parasternal view possible for echocardiography [207]
- Stratosphere Sign [207]
- Hyperechogenic line between chest wall and thymus [208].
- Stairway Sign: stairway-like arrangement of horizontal hyperechogenic reflections due to trapped air below the thymus [209].

8.2.21 Pneumothorax

The first report on the diagnosis of a pneumothorax by ultrasound in humans was published by Wernecke et al. in 1987 [210], highlighting the absence of lung sliding and B-lines.

The ESPNIC POCUS guidelines state that lung ultrasound is helpful and effective in detecting pneumothorax [143]. Lung ultrasound is efficient in the diagnosis of pneumothorax [38, 211, 212] and at least equal compared to chest-X-ray [211, 212] with a sensitivity of 82.9-99 % (95 % CI: 78.3-98 % to 86.9-100 %) and a specificity of 98-98.2 % (95 % CI: 94-97 % to 99 %) if chest-X-ray was used as reference, in two systematic reviews with meta-analysis [211, 212].

In a prospective observational study lung ultrasound had a sensitivity of 90.9 % and a specificity of 98.9 % [145].

There is one retrospective study evaluating the efficacy of lung ultrasound and chest-X-ray using computed tomography or aspiration of air as a reference. In this study, lung ultrasound was superior to chest-X-ray [213].

Lung ultrasound is faster in diagnosing pneumothorax with 5.3 min and a standard deviation of 5.6 min compared to chest X-ray with 19 min and a standard deviation of 11.7 min

Lung ultrasound can be used to diagnose pneumothorax in neonates during resuscitation [214]. Lung ultrasound should be used during ventilation as lung sliding can be missed during chest-compressions. Lung pulse is hard to interpret in this situations [214].

Especially if pneumothorax occurs in atypical localisations, lung ultrasound is of great advantage [215].

Interestingly, small pneumothoraces can be diagnosed in 10.3% of asymptomatic children [216].

- Absence of lung sliding [14, 40, 61, 211, 217, 218]
Sensitivity: 82.1% (95% CI: 71.7-89.8%), specificity: 100 (95% CI: 97.6-100%) [211]
Sensitivity: 100%, specificity 100% [213]
- Stratosphere Sign in M-mode [14, 40, 218]
- Absence of lung pulse [40, 213]
Sensitivity: 100%, specificity: 100% [213]
Because of its relative proximity to the heart, this sign is difficult to interpret in neonates. Lung pulse can also be seen in tension pneumothorax [214].
- Lung point [14, 39, 40, 211, 217, 218]
Sensitivity: 87.2% (95% CI: 77.7-93.7%), specificity: 99.4 (95% CI: 96.5-100%) [211]
Sensitivity: 94.28%, specificity: 100% [213]
- Absence of B-lines in affected area [14, 40, 61, 217, 218]
Sensitivity: 100%, specificity 100% [213]
- Mirrored Ribs: at least one clear reflection of at least one rib and intercostal structures in B-mode [90].
- A-lines behind the sternum in transversal view [219].

Diagnosis following Liu et al. protocol [218]

1. Identify pleural line, A-lines and B-lines in B-mode
2. Identify lung sliding and lung point
3. Identify stratosphere sign in M-mode

Figure 8.2: Diagnose Flowchart Pneumothorax, Liu et al. [218]

Quantifying and Size

In adults, the position of the lung point is associated with the size of pneumothorax measured in computed tomography, this is superior to chest-X-ray and classic graduations. Volpicelli et al. showed that the median axillary line (correlates to $\geq 30\%$ collapsed lung) is the best anatomical cut-off between severe and mild forms of pneumothorax, see Table 8.2.

If a pneumothorax with a collapsed lung of $\leq 15\%$ is treated conservatively, the recurrence rate is significantly lower compared to interventionally treated [220,221]. This size correlates to the position of the lung point being anterior to the median axillary line. Supporting this landmark in neonates, Montero et al. calculated that an absent lung point or a lung point located in the posterior axillary line has a positive predictive value of 86.1% for pleural drainage [222].

In suspected severe pneumothorax in lung ultrasound but completely stable clinical condition of the patient, sequestration of the lung or cystic pulmonary airway malformation (CPAM) has to be considered as a differential diagnosis and evaluated. Furthermore, hyperinflation or interstitial emphysema can cause severely diminished lung sliding [166]. Ultrasound imaging alone is no indication for drainage.

Liu et al. established a classification system based on lung ultrasound signs, see Table 8.2.

Dynamic Evaluation

For dynamic evaluation, the lung point is marked with a pen per intercostal space on the skin. In timely reevaluation (e.g. 1 h) size of the pneumothorax can be assessed (increase, stable, decrease).

This method is not validated in humans, but is efficient and tested in animal study [224].

Table 8.2: Classification of pneumothorax (PTX) size using lung ultrasound (LUS) and the position of lung point (LP) relative position to the median axillary line (MAL) compared to classification using computerized tomography (CT) by Volpicelli et al. [223] and Liu et al. [218].

Volpicelli et al. [223]		
Lung collaps in CT (%)	Lung point position in LUS	Predictive value (95 % CI)
Class 1 (≤ 10)	anterior to MAL	78,1 (59.7–90.9)
Class 2 (11 – 29)	on MAL	88.5 (69.8–97.6) - 97,5 (86.6–99.9)
Class 3 (≥ 30)	posterior to MAL	50 (26.0-74.0)
Liu et. al. [218]		
Category	Definition	
Mild PTX	PTX sign anterior. No lung sliding in $<50\%$ of lobe of the lung.	
Moderate PTX	PTX signs anterior and lateral. No lung sliding in $>50\%$ of lobe of the lung.	
Severe PTX	PTX sign anterior. No lung point visible.	

Ultrasound Guided Pleural Puncture by Liu et al. [218]

The ESPNIC POCUS guidelines state that lung ultrasound is helpful in performing chest tube placement or in pleural puncture of spontaneous pneumothorax. Ultrasound should be used before a chest tube is placed or a puncture performed to evaluate the lung borders and abdominal organs minimizing complication rate [143]. The child is placed in supine, lateral or prone position depending on the position of the pneumothorax. An elevated chest position helps to aspirate more air. If a severe pneumothorax is present, pleural puncture must be performed immediately. A mild pneumothorax can be treated conservatively, but might profit from drainage. In moderate pneumothorax, the pleural puncture should be performed in the area without detectable lung sliding. The pleural puncture is performed after sterile draping of the ultrasound machine and under direct needle guidance [218]. This method showed satisfactory results [215, 225] and allows for targeted puncture [215].

8.2.22 Pulmonary Congestion

Pulmonary congestions presents as interstitial syndrom [70].

8.2.23 Pulmonary Fibrosis

Pulmonary fibrosis is similar to bronchopulmonary dysplasia.

- Increased number of B-lines

- Consolidation

8.2.24 Pulmonary Hemorrhage of the Newborn

- Abnormal pleural line [14]
- Consolidation with aerobronchogram [14, 226]
- Shred sign [14, 226]
- Pleural effusion uni- or bilateral [14]

If consolidation, aerobronchogram and pleural effusion were visible, the sensitivity was 81 % and 98.4 % [226].

8.2.25 Pulmonary Hypertension

The combination of lung ultrasound and double doppler Tei index performed well in the assessment of the right ventricular function and lung condition of neonates with pulmonary hypertension [227], but the diagnostic value has to be assessed.

8.2.26 Respiratory Distress Syndrome

The ESPNIC guideline state that lung ultrasound is helpful to differentiate between respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) and transient tachypnoea of the newborn (TTN) [143]. Lung ultrasound has the same accuracy compared to chest-X-ray in the diagnosis of RDS [72, 228, 229] with a sensitivity of 92-99 % (95 % CI: 89-92 % to 94-100 %) and a specificity of 95 % (95 % CI: 87-93 % to 97-98 %) if chest-X-ray was used as reference in two systematic reviews with meta-analysis [228, 229].

Lung ultrasound can be effective to differentiate between RDS and TTN [230, 231]. In RDS, abnormalities are detectable within the whole lung and the pleural line is rough with consolidations [231], in TTN the alveations are seen mainly in the basal and dorsal areas with a smooth pleural line and the absence of consolidations the pleural line remains smooth and there are no consolidations. In the first 72 h the neoantes with RDS have worse lung aeration and oxygenation compared to TTN [232].

- Thickened and rough pleural line [14, 59, 63, 72, 127, 143, 233, 234, 235, 236, 237, 238, 239, 240, 241]
- Consolidations [63, 127, 143, 145, 234, 235, 236, 237, 239, 240, 241], especially posterior [14], occasionally with aerobronchogram [14, 236]
With snowflake sign: consolidations with many bronchograms [127, 239].

- White lung (=coalescent B-Lines) [59, 63, 72, 127, 143, 233, 234, 238, 240]
- Abnormalities in all areas [14, 59, 63, 72, 234, 238, 241]
- No A-lines [143, 237, 241]
- No mirroring of the liver or spleen in subcostal transversal view [63]

Zheng et al. [240] differentiated between severe and non-severe RDS and achieved high accuracy with a sensitivity of 73.3 %, a specificity of 93.8 %, a positive predictive value of 91.7 % and a negative predictive value of 78.9 % using the following criteria for severe RDS

- Thickened or rough pleural line
- Coalescent B-lines
- Consolidations

Surfactant Application

The need for surfactant replacement can be evaluated using lung ultrasound [242] with sensitivity of 86 % (95 % CI: 81-90 %) and specificity of 82 % (95 % CI: 79-95 %) if chest-X-ray was used as a reference in one systematic review with meta-analysis [243]. This assessment can be performed 20-30 min after birth and has a higher accuracy compared to chest-X-ray [244]. After surfactant application, changes are visible in lung ultrasound after a delay [59, 237]. The score decreases significantly over 24 h [242]. After 4 h the number of consolidations and the number of B-lines decrease while the areas with A-lines increase [237] especially in anterior areas [245]. After 6 h the image is normalised, the B-lines are significantly reduced and A-lines are visible. [63, 237] If the patient does not respond to surfactant therapy, this can be indicative of alveolar capillary dysplasia [246].

Ventilation

The need for ventilation can be assessed using six different image constellations [247]. Basically, this is an adaption of the widely used lung ultrasound score.

Score and Respiratory Distress Syndrome

In a systematic review with meta-analysis of 1162 patients, the best cut-off for predicting surfactant application was 5 with a sensitivity of 94 % (95 % CI: 85-97 %) and specificity of 79 % (95 % CI: 31-97 %) [243].

The different possibilities to detect the development of RDS in lung ultrasound and the

Table 8.3: Different cut-off levels in lung ultrasound score to predict need for ventilation or surfactant in RDS with corresponding sensitivity (Sen), specificity (Spe), negative predictive value (NPV) and positive predictive value (PPV) and patient characteristics (number and mean/median gestational age) of studies (observational study (OS), systematic review (SR)) and references. Almost all studies used six views (left and right: anterior upper, anterior lower, lateral).

1. Surfactant							
Score (views)	Sen (%)	Spe (%)	NPV (%)	PPV (%)	n (GA)	Type	Reference
>2 (6)	91	25	93	20	65 (30 SSW)	OS	[92]
>12 (6)	92.9	92.5	97.4	81.3	62 (29-31 SSW)	OS	[248]
>4 (6)	100	61	97	54	65 (30 SSW)	OS	[92]
>6 (6)	90	80	88	82	133 (28 SSW)	OS	[98]
>8 (6)	82	92	83	88	133 (28 SSW)	OS	[98]
>4 (6)	96	100			45 (30 SSW)	OS	[249]
> 9 (6)	79	84	82	79	240 (29.5 SSW)	OS	[242]
> 9 (6)	69	90	92	64	62 (36 SSW)	OS	[250]
2. Surfactant							
>10 (6), 2h n 1.Surf	94	60	95	56	46 (32 SSW)	OS	[251]
Ventilation							
>25.5 (12)	81.3	88.8			146 (29 SSW)	OS	[106]
>12 (6)	100	77.6	100	31.2	62 (29-31 SSW)	OS	[248]
>8 (12)	74	68.3			104 (<32 SSW)	OS	[102]
>7 (12)	75.3	83.6			355 (32-37 SSW)	OS	[102]
Ventilation/Surfactant							
>5-6 (6)	88	82			485	SR	[252]

need for ventilation is shown in Table 8.2.26. Almost all studies used six views (left and right: anterior cranial, anterior caudal, lateral). Starting from nCPAP with 6 cmH₂O in RDS a change in ventilation mode to 6-12cmH₂O leads to significant improvement of lung ultrasound scores and oxygenation after 2 h [99].

Raimondi et al. used an adapted version of the lung ultrasound score with six views: posterior and anterior axillary line as well as medioclavicular line [242].

Lung ultrasound score in 12 areas correlates with PaO_2/FiO_2 [238]. A score of 13 in 12 areas can diagnose RDS with a sensitivity of 96.9% and a specificity of 93.3% [238].

8.2.27 Sequester of the Lung

- Consolidation in affected area [194, 196]
- Absence of pleural line in affected area [194, 196]
- Abnormal feeding vessel [194, 196]

8.2.28 Subglottic Hematoma

Ultrasound can detect a subglottic hematoma as cause of a stridor [253]. In case of subglottic hematoma there is a consolidation in the trachea [253].

8.2.29 Transient Tachypnoea of the Newborn

Corresponds to wet lung [14]. The ESPNIC guideline state that lung ultrasound is helpful to differentiate between RDS and TTN [143]. Lung ultrasound has the same accuracy compared to chest-X-ray in the diagnosis of TTN [72, 254] with a sensitivity of 55-98 % (95 % CI: 51-92 % to 58-100 %) and a specificity of 98-99 % (95 % CI: 98-91 % to 99-100 %) if chest-X-ray was used as reference in a systematic review with meta-analysis [254].

In a prospective observational study lung ultrasound had a sensitivity of 100 % and a specificity of 100 % [145].

Lung ultrasound score can be used to document the progression or regression of TTN. After 3 d no significant findings compared to a healthy control can be seen [255].

Lung ultrasound can be effective to differentiate between RDS and TTN [230, 231]. In RDS, abnormalities are detectable in the whole lung and the pleural line is rough with consolidations [231], in TTN the changes are mainly visible in the basal and dorsal areas, the pleural line remains smooth and there are no consolidations. This differentiation is consistent with the optimal cut-off level for lung ultrasound score for the detection of TTN with 6.5 in 6 views [256] corresponding to a white lung without consolidations in every area.

In the first 72 h neonates with TTN have better lung aeration and oxygenation compared to RDS [232].

- Can start with a white lung [14]
- Thickened or blurred (regular) pleural line [14, 39, 84, 143, 235]
- No consolidations [14, 39, 84, 145, 235]
- Double lung point possible: coalescent B-lines in inferior areas and less coalescent B-lines in anterior/superior areas; uni- or bilateral [14, 39, 63, 72, 84, 143, 145, 201, 257]
Sensitivity: 67 % (95 % CI: 63-71 %), specificity: 97 % (95 % CI: 95-98 %) [258]
Sensitivity: 85.9 %, specificity: 94.4 % [257]
or
increased non coalescent B-lines uni- or bilateral [39, 84]

8.2.30 Tuberculosis

In children lung ultrasound can be used to diagnose pulmonary tuberculosis [21]

- Subpleural nodules
- Consolidations
- Pleural effusion
- Pericardial effusion

the

8.2.31 Tuberos Sclerosis

Lung ultrasound can guide the diagnostics for tuberous sclerosis [259].

- Hyperechoic lesions up to 2 cm confined to the myocardium [259].

Chapter 9

Lung Ultrasound in Critical Situations

Lung ultrasound can be used efficiently in critical situations by experienced users. Structured studies are scarce for this indication. Bilateral ventilation can be verified within 15 s but clear recommendations are missing up to date [260]. In the evaluation of a desaturation in a ventilated child, the first four letters of the acronym DOPES (Dislocation, Obstruction, Pneumothorax, Equipment and Stomach) can be assessed using lung ultrasound. Bilateral lung sliding and visualising the endotracheal tube in the trachea excludes dislocation, obstruction, pneumothorax and partially equipment failure [260].

Chapter 10

Lung Ultrasound and Procedures

10.1 Weaning from Extracorporeal Membrane Oxygenation

Lung ultrasound can evaluate the aeration of the lung during weaning from ECMO [47].

10.2 Targeted Ventilation using Lung Ultrasound

10.2.1 Position of Endotracheal Tube

It is unclear whether a lung ultrasound can be used to confirm the correct position of an endotracheal tube. It is possible to visualize the tube directly. Visualizations of bilateral lung sliding was inefficient to confirm correct position of an endotracheal tube in an observational study in a PICU [261].

Method by Dincer et al. [262]

An intratracheal image is obtained from the sagittal area with the aortic arch and right pulmonary artery, in a high parasternal plane. First, the tip of the ETT is located, and to ensure the position, the ETT is moved back and forth approximately 0.2 cm. Then the arcus aorta and right pulmonary artery are visualized by slightly tilting the probe. The measurement of tip to carina distance is assessed by assuming that the upper end of the right pulmonary artery level is equal to the carina. The distance between the upper end of the pulmonary artery and the ETT is measured. This measurement correlates with chest-X-ray, but is six times faster.

10.2.2 Targeted Recruitment

Lung ultrasound score was able to detect large changes in total and regional lung volume in real time and correctly identified opening and closing pressures but lacked the precision to detect small changes in lung volume [110].

Recruitment During Ventilation

Lung ultrasound can be used for recruitment on conventional ventilation [263]. Shady et al. defined the MAP at which consolidated areas in posterior lung fields are opened as P_{Open} and the MAP under gradual reduction at which they revert to increased B-lines or consolidations as P_{Close} . The MAP was then set 2 mbar above the P_{Close} [264].

A very similar protocol was followed by Pierro et al. [81]. They defined a S pattern as ring-down artifacts starting from consolidations after raising the PEEP or continuous distension pressure (CDP), called S(unray) pattern (see Chapter 7.2.21), [80] to detect recruitability.

In the protocol, as in Shady et al. [264], the PEEP/CDP is increased by 1cm H_2O every 1-2 min until consolidations disappear, this corresponds to the P_{Open} , and then reduced again until consolidations appear, this corresponds to the P_{Close} . The optimal PEEP/CDP was chosen closely above the P_{Close} [81].

Lung ultrasound during laparoscopic surgery and subsequent recruitment reduces the incidence of atelectasis in infants under 3 months at age [263].

10.2.3 Determining Lung Expansion during High-Frequency Oscillatory Ventilation with Lung Ultrasound

Lung ultrasound can be used to assess lung expansion based on rib counting during high-frequency oscillatory ventilation with a difference of -2 compared to chest X-ray. The examination is conducted in the supine position with the probe at the right midclavicular line. Ribs are counted along the craniocaudal axis without lifting the probe until the hemidiaphragm is seen. For instance, if counted rib 7, this corresponds to rib 7, it equates to rib 9 in chest X-ray measurements. [265]

10.2.4 PEEP determination

If lung ultrasound can be used to optimize PEEP is currently evaluated in a randomized controlled trial [266].

10.2.5 Extubation

In 2023, a systematic review of the literature concluded that lung ultrasound is promising in predicting neonatal extubation failure, but the studies are heterogenous and therefore large scale prospective trials are needed [267]. The pooled sensitivity is 82 % and the specificity 83 % [267].

In preterm infants born <32 weeks of gestation, a lung ultrasound score <11.5 predicted extubation success with highest sensitivity and a score <7.5 with highest specificity on the 3rd and 7th day after birth [114].

In 80 intubated neonates (mean gestational age 34 weeks) a score of ≤ 4 predicted extubation success with a sensitivity of 83 % and a specificity of 88 % before and a score of ≤ 6 with a sensitivity of 89 % and specificity of 90 % after 6 h [112]. Six regions were scanned: two anterior (cranial and caudal) and one lateral view [112].

In 314 intubated neonates (mean gestational age 33 weeks) a score of <18 in 12 regions predicted extubation success with a sensitivity of 86.7 % and a specificity of 74.3 % [113].

In 45 preterm infants with gestational age under 28 weeks, the adapted Szymanski-score with 5 categories [121] in two anterior and lateral views over 15 was associated with an extubation failure [122].

10.2.6 Weaning from nCPAP

Lung ultrasound can be used to detect readiness for weaning from nCPAP [268]. A score below 8 had a sensitivity of 88 % and a specificity of 90 % for successful discontinuation of nCPAP [268].

10.3 Targeted Therapy using Lung Ultrasound

10.3.1 Targeted Surfactant Therapy by Rodriguez-Fanjul et al. [49]

In a prospective randomised controlled study, 56 preterm infants with a gestational age <32 weeks gestation were assessed using lung ultrasound score versus clinical parameters based on FiO_2 .

1. LUS within 1 h in 6 regions (anterior, lateral and posterior)
2. Score >8: Surfactant therapy

The lung ultrasound group received surfactant earlier at lower FiO_2 values, without influence on ventilation days, BPD or hospital stay [49]. If lung ultrasound is used to guide surfactant therapy, usage can be reduced by 30.1 % without undertreatment [269].

10.3.2 Targeted Diuretic Therapy

In patients with lung edema (interstitial syndrome or alveolar syndrome) the diuretic therapy can be monitored using lung ultrasound [77, 78]. This method was used by Lo et al. to treat an infant receiving intraoperative fluid resuscitation showing increased work of breathing after extubation with furosemid effectively [270].

10.3.3 Targeted Positioning

Position changes should be considered, whenever posterior consolidations are visible [78].

10.3.4 Dexamethasone Therapy

The effect of a low dose dexamethasone therapy can be monitored with lung ultrasound [78].

10.3.5 Targeted Bronchoalveolar Lavage by Liu et al. [271]

Liu et al. used lung ultrasound for the need of bronchoalveolar lavage in 35 neonates [271]. Recruitment and lavage were performed until no consolidations were visible [271].

10.3.6 Targeted Physiotherapy

Lung ultrasound allows the targeted application of physiotherapy [48] and its success by monitoring atelectasis. This is particularly relevant and feasible when the patient should be mobilized as little as possible, e.g. on ECMO [48].

10.3.7 Targeted Puncture

Pneumatocele

Muniraman et al. successfully punctured a pneumatocele lung ultrasound guided [272].

10.4 Lung Ultrasound after Central Venous Line Placement

In the context of a central venous line placement, a quick look at the lungs in terms of a Fast-LUS can detect periprocedural complications (PTX, etc.).

10.5 Lung Ultrasound and Thoracic Ultrasound in Cases of Non Accidental Injury

Lung ultrasound and especially thoracic ultrasound with a focus on the ribs and corresponding fractures represents a rapid and sensitive diagnostic tool in case of suspected child abuse [273]. Appropriate training and experience are essential.

Chapter 11

Implementation and Digitalisation of Lung Ultrasound

11.1 Implementation

At the University of Manitoba, Canada, lung ultrasound was introduced as first line diagnostic in 2016. Chest X-ray is only performed when results of lung ultrasound were inconclusive or rare diseases were suspected. At first only physicians were trained in lung ultrasound, but since 2019 also respiratory therapists and nurse practitioners are trained [8].

11.2 Digitalisation

Bassiouny et al. have created a promising machine learning model for lung ultrasound that also allows clinician assessment [274]. Wu et al. have been able to diagnose respiratory distress syndrome with an AUC of 0.96 using Artificial Intelligence Algorithm [275].

Implementing computer-assisted image analyses might improve the precision of lung ultrasound [52].

Chapter 12

Outlook

12.1 Lung Ultrasound and Electric Impedance Tomography

In a preterm lamb model, He et al. showed that lung ultrasound can detect inhomogeneous lung aeration in dependent and non-dependent areas when compared to electric impedance tomography [276]. If this can be reproduced in humans remains unclear but is plausible.

12.2 Surfactant need

In 2023, a meta-analysis of clinical decision thresholds for surfactant administration in preterm infants only found one study using lung ultrasound [49] and therefore concluded lung ultrasound may be a very promising tool determine surfactant requirement [277].

12.3 Artificial Intelligence

Combining lung ultrasound with artificial intelligence augmentation to detect pneumonia showed promising results [278] as did the prediction of need for surfactant and nasal CPAP in neonates with tachypnoea, dyspnoea or oxygen requirement [250].

12.4 Cardiopulmonary Ultrasound

The combination of neonatologist performed echocardiography and neonatologist performed lung ultrasound might be beneficial [71].

Bibliography

- [1] Lichtenstein DA. BLUE-protocol and FALLS-protocol: two applications of lung ultrasound in the critically ill. *Chest*. 2015;147(6):1659–1670.
- [2] Aichhorn L, Küng E, Schwabegger B. Neonatologist performed lung ultrasound: NPLUS—proposal for a consistent ultrasound terminology. *Frontiers in Pediatrics*. 2023;10:1007672.
- [3] Jonusas SF, Criolioli CM, De Gregorio AS. Basic notions of lung ultrasound in neonatology. *Acceso abierto*. 2022;264:356.
- [4] Tandircioglu UA, Yigit S, Oguz B, Kayki G, Celik HT, Yurdakok M. Lung ultrasonography decreases radiation exposure in newborns with respiratory distress: a retrospective cohort study. *European Journal of Pediatrics*. 2022;181(3):1029–1035.
- [5] Escourrou G, De Luca D. Lung ultrasound decreased radiation exposure in preterm infants in a neonatal intensive care unit. *Acta Paediatrica (Oslo, Norway: 1992)*. 2016;105(5):e237–9.
- [6] Rodriguez-Fanjul J, Benet N, de Liria CRG, Porta R, Guinovart G, Bobillo-Pérez S. Lung ultrasound protocol decreases radiation in newborn population without side effects: A quality improvement project. *Medicina intensiva*. 2023;47(1):16–22.
- [7] Caroselli C, Blaivas M, Falzetti S. Diagnostic imaging in newborns, children and adolescents infected with severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2): is there a realistic alternative to lung high-resolution computed tomography (HRCT) and chest X-rays? A systematic review of the literature. *Ultrasound in Medicine & Biology*. 2021;47(11):3034–3040.
- [8] Elsayed Y, Narvey M, Lashin A, Alammary D, Gigolyk S, Louis D. Point of care lung ultrasound service in neonatal intensive care: Five years of experience in Manitoba, Canada. *Journal of Perinatology*. 2022;p. 1–5.

- [9] Gao YQ, Qiu RX, Liu J, Zhang L, Ren XL, Qin SJ. Lung ultrasound completely replaced chest X-ray for diagnosing neonatal lung diseases: a 3-year clinical practice report from a neonatal intensive care unit in China. *The Journal of Maternal-Fetal & Neonatal Medicine*. 2020;p. 1–8.
- [10] Liu J, Zhang X, Wang Y, Li J, Yan W, Qin SJ, et al. The outcome-or cost-effectiveness analysis of LUS-based care or CXR-based care of neonatal lung diseases: the clinical practice evidence from a level three NICU in China. *Diagnostics*. 2022;12(11):2790.
- [11] Corsini I, Parri N, Ficial B, Ciarcia M, Migliaro F, Capasso L, et al. Lung ultrasound in Italian neonatal intensive care units: a national survey. *Pediatric Pulmonology*. 2022;57(9):2199–2206.
- [12] Montasser M, Kirolos S, Milan A, Meau-Petit V. Neonatal point-of-care lung ultrasound: a UK-wide survey and the way forward. *Archives of Disease in Childhood-Fetal and Neonatal Edition*. 2023;108(4):431–432.
- [13] Palamattam DJ, Sreedhar R, Gadhinglajkar SV, Dash PK, Sukesan S. Bedside Chest Ultrasound in Postoperative Pediatric Cardiac Surgery Patients: Comparison With Bedside Chest Radiography. *Journal of Cardiothoracic and Vascular Anesthesia*. 2022;36(11):4039–4044.
- [14] Liu J, Copetti R, Sorantin E, Lovrenski J, Rodriguez-Fanjul J, Kurepa D, et al. Protocol and guidelines for point-of-care lung ultrasound in diagnosing neonatal pulmonary diseases based on international expert consensus. *JoVE (Journal of Visualized Experiments)*. 2019;(145):e58990.
- [15] Rath C, Nagpal R, Suryawanshi P. Point-of-Care Ultrasound in Neonatology in India: The Way Forward. *Indian Pediatrics*. 2023;60(5):351–357.
- [16] de Mendoza BdRH, Sanchez-de Toledo J, Perez SB, Girona M, Gargallo MB, Rodriguez-Fanjul J. Lung ultrasound to assess the etiology of persistent pulmonary hypertension of the newborn (LUPPHYN study): a pilot study. *Neonatology*. 2019;116(2):140–146.
- [17] Merli L, Nanni L, Curatola A, Pellegrino M, De Santis M, Silvaroli S, et al. Congenital lung malformations: a novel application for lung ultrasound? *Journal of Ultrasound*. 2021;24(3):349–353.
- [18] Jagła M, Grudzień A, Starzec K, Tomasik T, Zasada M, Kwinta P. Lung ultrasound in the diagnosis of neonatal respiratory failure prior to patient transport. *Journal of Clinical Ultrasound*. 2019;47(9):518–525.

- [19] Navarro MR, Armisén AD, Rodríguez JG, Jover MP. Lung ultrasound imaging used during transport of patients with neonatal respiratory compromise. *Emergencias*. 2023;35:225–232.
- [20] Di Nardo M, Lorusso R, Guner Y, Schomberg J, De Luca D. Feasibility of lung ultrasound to monitor aeration in children supported with extracorporeal membrane oxygenation for severe acute respiratory distress syndrome. *Asaio Journal*. 2021;67(6):e104–e106.
- [21] Moretó-Planas L, Sagrado MJ, Mahajan R, Gallo J, Biague E, Gonçalves R, et al. Point-of-care ultrasound for tuberculosis diagnosis in children: a Médecins Sans Frontières cross-sectional study in Guinea-Bissau. *BMJ open*. 2023;13(5):e066937.
- [22] Schwarz S. Pulmonary Sonography–Neonatal Diagnosis Part 2. *Ultraschall in der Medizin-European Journal of Ultrasound*. 2023;44(03):240–268.
- [23] Kazi S, Hernstadt H, Abo YN, Graham H, Palmer M, Graham SM, et al. The utility of chest x-ray and lung ultrasound in the management of infants and children presenting with severe pneumonia in low-and middle-income countries: A pragmatic scoping review. *Journal of global health*. 2022;12.
- [24] Khera D, Krishna D. Point-of-Care Thoracic Ultrasound in Children with Bronchiolitis: Authors' Reply. *Indian Journal of Pediatrics*. 2022;89(11):1162–1162.
- [25] Corsini I, Parri N, Gozzini E, Coviello C, Leonardi V, Poggi C, et al. Lung ultrasound for the differential diagnosis of respiratory distress in neonates. *Neonatology*. 2019;115(1):77–84.
- [26] DeSanti RL, Cowan EA, Kory PD, Lasarev MR, Schmidt J, Al-Subu AM. The Inter-Rater Reliability of Pediatric Point-of-Care Lung Ultrasound Interpretation in Children With Acute Respiratory Failure. *Journal of Ultrasound in Medicine*. 2022;41(5):1159–1167.
- [27] Rodríguez-Fanjul J, Ginovart G, et al. E-learning curriculum on newborn point-of-care lung ultrasound for Paediatric residents. In: *Anales de Pediatría*; 2022.
- [28] Guitart C, Esteban E, Becerra J, Rodríguez-Fanjul J, Cambra FJ, Balaguer M, et al. A training plan to implement lung ultrasound for diagnosing pneumonia in children. *Pediatric research*. 2022;92(4):1115–1121.
- [29] Athanasia V, Savvas DP, Soutana F, Marianna SR, Maria A, Katerina K. Neonatal intensive care unit nurse training in identifying ultrasound landmarks in the neonatal mediastinum. A training program for nurses in North-Eastern Greece. *Journal of Pediatric Nursing*. 2022;.

- [30] Elsayed Y, Sheldon J, Gigolyk S. The Impact of Respiratory Therapist Performed Point-of-Care Lung Ultrasound on the Respiratory Care in Neonates, Manitoba Experience, Canada. *American Journal of Perinatology*. 2023;.
- [31] Gomond-Le Goff C, Vivalda L, Foligno S, Loi B, Yousef N, De Luca D. Effect of different probes and expertise on the interpretation reliability of point-of-care lung ultrasound. *Chest*. 2020;157(4):924–931.
- [32] Rojas-García A, Moreno-Blanco D, Otero-Arteseros M, Rubio-Bolívar FJ, Peinado H, Elorza-Fernández D, et al. SIMUNEO: Control and Monitoring System for Lung Ultrasound Examination and Treatment of Neonatal Pneumothorax and Thoracic Effusion. *Sensors*. 2023;23(13):5966.
- [33] Sande R, Jenderka KV, Moran CM, Marques S, Diaz JJ, Ter Haar G, et al. Safety Aspects of Perinatal Ultrasound. *Ultraschall in der Medizin-European Journal of Ultrasound*. 2021;35.
- [34] Miller DL, Dou C, Dong Z. Lung Ultrasound Induction of Pulmonary Capillary Hemorrhage in Rats With Consideration of Exposimetric Relationships to Previous Similar Observations in Neonatal Swine. *Ultrasound in Medicine & Biology*. 2023;49(6):1441–1448.
- [35] Miller DL, Dou C, Dong Z. Frame Rate Exposimetry for Pulmonary Capillary Hemorrhage During Lung Ultrasound. *Journal of Ultrasound in Medicine*. 2023;.
- [36] Mongodi S, De Luca D, Colombo A, Stella A, Santangelo E, Corradi F, et al. Quantitative lung ultrasound: technical aspects and clinical applications. *Anesthesiology*. 2021;134(6):949–965.
- [37] De Luca D, Alonso Ojembarrena A, Raimondi F. Scientific Evidence Is the Only Common Ground for the Debate on Neonatal Lung Ultrasound. *Neonatology*. 2023;120(3):17–18.
- [38] Musolino AM, Tomà P, De Rose C, Pitaro E, Boccuzzi E, De Santis R, et al. Ten years of pediatric lung ultrasound: a narrative review. *Frontiers in Physiology*. 2022;p. 2237.
- [39] Sharma D, Farahbakhsh N. Role of chest ultrasound in neonatal lung disease: a review of current evidences. *The Journal of Maternal-Fetal & Neonatal Medicine*. 2019;32(2):310–316.
- [40] Kurepa D, Zaghoul N, Watkins L, Liu J. Neonatal lung ultrasound exam guidelines. *Journal of Perinatology*. 2018;38(1):11.

- [41] Liu J, Guo G, Kurepa D, Volpicelli G, Sorantin E, Lovrenski J, et al. Specification and guideline for technical aspects and scanning parameter settings of neonatal lung ultrasound examination. *The Journal of Maternal-Fetal & Neonatal Medicine*. 2022;35(5):1003–1016.
- [42] Fernández LR, Hernández RG, Guerediaga IS, Gato JM, Fanjul JR, Bilbao VA, et al. Usefulness of lung ultrasound in the diagnosis and follow-up of respiratory diseases in neonates. *Anales de Pediatría (English Edition)*. 2022;96(3):252–e1.
- [43] Sartorius V, Loi B, Vivalda L, Regiroli G, de la Rubia Ortega S, Centorrino R, et al. Ultra-high frequency lung ultrasound in preterm neonates: a test validation study on interpretation agreement and reliability. *Archives of Disease in Childhood-Fetal and Neonatal Edition*. 2023;108(6):607–611.
- [44] Bhalla D, Naranje P, Jana M, Bhalla AS. Pediatric lung ultrasonography: current perspectives. *Pediatric Radiology*. 2022;p. 1–13.
- [45] Prontera G, Perri A, Vento G, D'Andrea V. Use of wireless ultrasound probe in isolated infants: a case report of two SARS-CoV-2-positive mothers' newborns. *Neonatology*. 2022;119(1):129–132.
- [46] Louis D, Belen K, Farooqui M, Idiong N, Amer R, Hussain A, et al. Prone versus supine position for lung ultrasound in neonates with respiratory distress. *American journal of perinatology*. 2019;.
- [47] Zhang X, Fu Y, Yue G, Yang S, Ju R. Lung ultrasound for the assessment of lung recruitment in neonates with massive pneumothorax during extracorporeal membrane oxygenation: a case report. *Journal of Artificial Organs*. 2022;25(2):163–169.
- [48] Shkurka E, Nolan W. Physiotherapy-led lung ultrasound in neonatal extra-corporeal membrane oxygenation: A case-study. *Perfusion*. 2022;p. 02676591221094410.
- [49] Rodriguez-Fanjul J, Jordan I, Balaguer M, Batista-Muñoz A, Ramon M, Bobillo-Perez S. Early surfactant replacement guided by lung ultrasound in preterm newborns with RDS: the ULTRASURF randomised controlled trial. *European Journal of Pediatrics*. 2020;179(12):1913–1920.
- [50] Via G, Storti E, Gulati G, Neri L, Mojoli F, Braschi A, et al. Lung ultrasound in the ICU: from diagnostic instrument to respiratory monitoring tool. *Minerva Anestesiol*. 2012;78(11):1282–1296.

- [51] Shen J, Du Y, Sun Y, Huang X, Zhou J, Chen C. Modified lung ultrasound score for bronchopulmonary dysplasia predicts late respiratory outcomes in preterm infants. *Pediatric Pulmonology*. 2023;58(9):2551–2558.
- [52] Sett A, Foo GW, Kenna KR, Sutton RJ, Perkins EJ, Sourial M, et al. Quantitative lung ultrasound detects dynamic changes in lung recruitment in the preterm lamb. *Pediatric Research*. 2023;93(6):1591–1598.
- [53] Pryor E, Davies I, Crossley K, Thiel A, McGillick E, Rodgers K, et al. Assessing lung aeration using ultrasound after birth in near-term lambs at risk of respiratory distress. *Frontiers in Pediatrics*. 2023;11:1148443.
- [54] Pryor EJ, Blank DA, Hooper SB, Crossley KJ, Badurdeen S, Pollock JA, et al. Quantifying lung aeration in neonatal lambs at birth using lung ultrasound. *Frontiers in Pediatrics*. 2022;10:990923.
- [55] Sett A, Kenna KR, Sutton RJ, Perkins EJ, Sourial M, Chapman JD, et al. Lung ultrasound of the dependent lung detects real-time changes in lung volume in the preterm lamb. *Archives of Disease in Childhood-Fetal and Neonatal Edition*. 2023;108(1):51–56.
- [56] Walsh P, Chaigneau FRC, Lebedev M, Mutua V, McEligot H, Lam SH, et al. Validating a bovine model for lung ultrasound of bronchiolitis. *Journal of ultrasound*. 2022;25(3):611–624.
- [57] Guo G, Zhang XF, Liu J, Zong HF. Lung ultrasound to quantitatively evaluate extravascular lung water content and its clinical significance. *The Journal of Maternal-Fetal & Neonatal Medicine*. 2022;35(15):2904–2914.
- [58] Elsayed YN, Hinton M, Graham R, Dakshinamurti S. Lung ultrasound predicts histological lung injury in a neonatal model of acute respiratory distress syndrome. *Pediatric pulmonology*. 2020;55(11):2913–2923.
- [59] Raimondi F, Yousef N, Migliaro F, Capasso L, De Luca D. Point-of-care lung ultrasound in neonatology: classification into descriptive and functional applications. *Pediatric research*. 2018;p. 1–8.
- [60] Łyżniak P, Świętoń D, Serafin Z, Szurowska E. Lung ultrasound in a nutshell. Lines, signs, some applications, and misconceptions from a radiologist's point of view. *Polish journal of radiology*. 2023;88:e294.
- [61] Ruoss JL, Bazaciu C, Cacho N, De Luca D. Lung Ultrasound in the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit: Does It Impact Clinical Care? *Children*. 2021;8(12):1098.

- [62] Schwarz S. Pulmonary sonography–neonatal diagnosis part 1. *Ultraschall in der Medizin-European Journal of Ultrasound*. 2023;44(01):14–35.
- [63] Mong A, Epelman M, Darge K. Ultrasound of the pediatric chest. *Pediatric radiology*. 2012;42(11):1287–1297.
- [64] Blank DA, Rogerson SR, Kamlin COF, Fox LM, Lorenz L, Kane SC, et al. Lung ultrasound during the initiation of breathing in healthy term and late preterm infants immediately after birth, a prospective, observational study. *Resuscitation*. 2017;114:59–65.
- [65] Blank DA, Kamlin COF, Rogerson SR, Fox LM, Lorenz L, Kane SC, et al. Lung ultrasound immediately after birth to describe normal neonatal transition: an observational study. *Archives of Disease in Childhood-Fetal and Neonatal Edition*. 2018;103(2):F157–F162.
- [66] Rea G, Sperandeo M, Di Serafino M, Vallone G, Tomà P. Neonatal and pediatric thoracic ultrasonography. *Journal of ultrasound*. 2019;p. 1–10.
- [67] Almudena AO, Alfonso María LS, Estefanía RG, Blanca GHM, Simón Pedro LL. Pleural line thickness reference values for preterm and term newborns. *Pediatric Pulmonology*. 2020;55(9):2296–2301.
- [68] Lichtenstein DA, Lascols N, Prin S, Meziere G. The "lung pulse": an early ultrasound sign of complete atelectasis. *Intensive Care Med*. 2003 Dec;29(12):2187–2192.
- [69] Lichtenstein DA, Mezière GA, Lagoueyte JF, Biderman P, Goldstein I, Gepner A. A-lines and B-lines: lung ultrasound as a bedside tool for predicting pulmonary artery occlusion pressure in the critically ill. *Chest*. 2009;136(4):1014–1020.
- [70] Parri N, Allinovi M, Giacalone M, Corsini I. To B or not to B. The rationale for quantifying B-lines in pediatric lung diseases. *Pediatric Pulmonology*. 2023;58(1):9–15.
- [71] Ciarmoli E, Storti E, Cangemi J, Leone A, Pierro M. Use of cardio-pulmonary ultrasound in the neonatal intensive care unit. *Children*. 2023;10(3):462.
- [72] Volpicelli G, Elbarbary M, Blaivas M, Lichtenstein DA, Mathis G, Kirkpatrick AW, et al. International evidence-based recommendations for point-of-care lung ultrasound. *Intensive care medicine*. 2012;38(4):577–591.
- [73] Martelius L, Süvari L, Janér C, Helve O, Kaskinen A, Kirjavainen T, et al. Lung ultrasound and static lung compliance during postnatal adaptation in healthy term infants. *Neonatology*. 2015;108(4):287–292.

- [74] Guo BB, Wang KK, Xie L, Liu XJ, Chen XY, Zhang F, et al. Comprehensive quantitative assessment of lung liquid clearance by lung ultrasound score in neonates with no lung disease during the first 24 hours. *BioMed Research International*. 2020;.
- [75] Lichtenstein DA. Current misconceptions in lung ultrasound: a short guide for experts. *Chest*. 2019;156(1):21–25.
- [76] Buonsenso D, De Rose C, Ferro V, Morello R, Musolino A, Valentini P. Lung ultrasound to detect cardiopulmonary interactions in acutely ill children. *Pediatric Pulmonology*. 2022;57(2):483–497.
- [77] Kasniya G, Weinberger B, Cerise J, Pulju M, Boyar V, Frunza F, et al. Lung ultrasound assessment of pulmonary edema in neonates with chronic lung disease before and after diuretic therapy. *Pediatric Pulmonology*. 2022;57(12):3145–3150.
- [78] Bruno G, Chioma R, Storti E, De Luca G, Fantinato M, Antonazzo P, et al. Targeted management of evolving and established chronic lung disease of prematurity assisted by cardiopulmonary ultrasound: A case report of four patients. *Frontiers in pediatrics*. 2023;10:1112313.
- [79] Allinovi M, Palazzini G, Lugli G, Gianassi I, Dallari L, Laudicina S, et al. Pre-dialysis B-line quantification at lung ultrasound is a useful method for evaluating the dry weight and predicting the risk of intradialytic hypotension. *Diagnostics*. 2022;12(12):2990.
- [80] Chioma R, Amabili L, Ciarmoli E, Copetti R, Villani P, Stella M, et al. The importance of lung recruitability: A novel ultrasound pattern to guide lung recruitment in neonates. *Journal of Neonatal-Perinatal Medicine*. 2022;(Preprint):1–11.
- [81] Pierro M, Chioma R, Ciarmoli E, Villani P, Storti E, Copetti R. Lung ultrasound guided pulmonary recruitment during mechanical ventilation in neonates: A case series. *Journal of Neonatal-Perinatal Medicine*. 2022;15(2):357–365.
- [82] Miller LE, Stoller JZ, Fraga MV. Point-of-care ultrasound in the neonatal ICU. *Current opinion in pediatrics*. 2020;32(2):216–227.
- [83] Matsumoto T, Matano H. The still lung point: new sonographic evidence for pneumomediastinum. *The American journal of emergency medicine*. 2016;34(2):344–e1.
- [84] Miall L, Wallis S. The management of respiratory distress in the moderately preterm newborn infant. *Archives of Disease in Childhood-Education and Practice*. 2011;96(4):128–135.

- [85] Liu J, Chen SW, Liu F, Li QP, Kong XY, Feng ZC. The diagnosis of neonatal pulmonary atelectasis using lung ultrasonography. *Chest*. 2015;147(4):1013–1019.
- [86] Gao S, Xiao T, Ju R, Ma R, Zhang X, Dong W. The application value of lung ultrasound findings in preterm infants with bronchopulmonary dysplasia. *Translational Pediatrics*. 2020;9(2):93.
- [87] Lichtenstein D, Mezière G, Seitz J. The dynamic air bronchogram: a lung ultrasound sign of alveolar consolidation ruling out atelectasis. *Chest*. 2009;135(6):1421–1425.
- [88] Ammirabile A, Buonsenso D, Di Mauro A. Lung ultrasound in pediatrics and neonatology: an update. In: *Healthcare*. vol. 9. MDPI; 2021. p. 1015.
- [89] Lichtenstein D. Pleural effusion and introduction to the lung ultrasound technique. *General ultrasound in the critically ill*. 2005;p. 96–104.
- [90] Küng E, Aichhorn L, Berger A, Werther T. Mirrored Ribs: A Sign for Pneumothorax in Neonates. *Pediatric Critical Care Medicine*. 2020;21(10):e944–e947.
- [91] Taveira M, Yousef N, Miatello J, Roy C, Claude C, Boutillier B, et al. Can a simple lung ultrasound score predict length of ventilation for infants with severe acute viral bronchiolitis? *Archives de pediatrie: organe officiel de la Societe francaise de pediatrie*. 2018;25(2):112–117.
- [92] Brat R, Yousef N, Klifa R, Reynaud S, Aguilera SS, De Luca D. Lung ultrasonography score to evaluate oxygenation and surfactant need in neonates treated with continuous positive airway pressure. *JAMA pediatrics*. 2015;169(8):e151797–e151797.
- [93] Alonso-Ojembarrena A, Mendez-Abad P, Alonso-Quintela P, Zafra-Rodríguez P, Oulego-Erroz I, Lubián-López SP. Lung ultrasound score has better diagnostic ability than NT-proBNP to predict moderate–severe bronchopulmonary dysplasia. *European Journal of Pediatrics*. 2022;p. 1–9.
- [94] Ollier V, Loi B, Rivaud C, Fortas F, Ruetsch V, Yousef N, et al. Semi-quantitative lung ultrasound score during ground transportation of outborn neonates with respiratory failure. *European Journal of Pediatrics*. 2022;181(8):3085–3092.
- [95] Yousef N, Vigo G, Shankar-Aguilera S, De Luca D. Semiquantitative Ultrasound Assessment of Lung Aeration Correlates With Lung Tissue Inflammation. *Ultrasound in Medicine & Biology*. 2020;.

- [96] Stoicescu ER, Manolescu DL, Iacob R, Cerbu S, Dima M, Iacob ER, et al. The Assessment of COVID-19 Pneumonia in Neonates: Observed by Lung Ultrasound Technique and Correlated with Biomarkers and Symptoms. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*. 2022;11(12):3555.
- [97] Martini S, Gatelli IF, Vitelli O, Vitali F, De Rienzo F, Parladori R, et al. Impact of patent ductus arteriosus on non-invasive assessments of lung fluids in very preterm infants during the transitional period. *European Journal of Pediatrics*. 2023;182(9):4247–4251.
- [98] De Martino L, Yousef N, Ben-Ammar R, Raimondi F, Shankar-Aguilera S, De Luca D. Lung ultrasound score predicts surfactant need in extremely preterm neonates. *Pediatrics*. 2018;142(3):e20180463.
- [99] Rodriguez-Fanjul J, Corsini I, Ortiz CS, Bobillo-Perez S, Raimondi F. Lung ultrasound to evaluate lung recruitment in neonates with respiratory distress (RELUS study). *Pediatric Pulmonology*. 2022;.
- [100] Loi B, Vigo G, Baraldi E, Raimondi F, Carnielli VP, Mosca F, et al. Lung ultrasound to monitor extremely preterm infants and predict bronchopulmonary dysplasia. A multicenter longitudinal cohort study. *American Journal of Respiratory and Critical Care Medicine*. 2021;203(11):1398–1409.
- [101] Yoon SJ, Han JH, Cho KH, Park J, Lee SM, Park MS. Tools for assessing lung fluid in neonates with respiratory distress. *BMC pediatrics*. 2022;22(1):1–7.
- [102] Zhang L, Feng J, Jin D, Yu Z, Qu Y, Zheng M, et al. Lung ultrasound score as a predictor of ventilator use in preterm infants with dyspnea within 24 h after dshospitalization. *Pediatrics & Neonatology*. 2023;.
- [103] Perri A, Sbordone A, Patti ML, Nobile S, Tirone C, Giordano L, et al. Early lung ultrasound score to predict noninvasive ventilation needing in neonates from 33 weeks of gestational age: A multicentric study. *Pediatric Pulmonology*. 2022;57(9):2227–2236.
- [104] Perri A, Riccardi R, Iannotta R, Di Molfetta DV, Arena R, Vento G, et al. Lung ultrasonography score versus chest X-ray score to predict surfactant administration in newborns with respiratory distress syndrome. *Pediatric pulmonology*. 2018;53(9):1231–1236.
- [105] Biasucci DG, Loi B, Centorrino R, Raschetti R, Piastra M, Pisapia L, et al. Ultrasound-assessed lung aeration correlates with respiratory system compliance in adults and neonates with acute hypoxemic restrictive respiratory failure: an observational prospective study. *Respiratory Research*. 2022;23(1):360.

- [106] Pang H, Zhang B, Shi J, Zang J, Qiu L. Diagnostic value of lung ultrasound in evaluating the severity of neonatal respiratory distress syndrome. *European journal of radiology*. 2019;116:186–191.
- [107] Tandircioglu UA, Melekoglu NA. Prospective Evaluation of the Correlation of Lung Ultrasonography Score and Blood Gas Parameters in Neonates With Respiratory Distress. *Cureus*. 2023;15(7).
- [108] Di Mauro A, Cappiello AR, Ammirabile A, Abbondanza N, Bianchi FP, Tafuri S, et al. Lung Ultrasound and Clinical Progression of Acute Bronchiolitis: A Prospective Observational Single-Center Study. *Medicina*. 2020;56(6):314.
- [109] Pungertnik T, Uros K, Panjan D, Krivec J. DIAGNOSTIC VALUE OF LUNG ULTRASOUND IN NEWBORNS AND INFANTS WITH BRONCHIOLITIS. In: 3rd LAUNCH, Lung Ultrasound in Neonates and Children; 2021. .
- [110] Sett A, Kenna KR, Sutton RJ, Perkins EJ, Sourial M, Chapman JD, et al. Lung ultrasound of the dependent lung detects real-time changes in lung volume in the preterm lamb. *Archives of Disease in Childhood-Fetal and Neonatal Edition*. 2022;.
- [111] Perri A, Fattore S, D'Andrea V, Sbordone A, Patti ML, Nobile S, et al. Lowering of the Neonatal Lung Ultrasonography Score after nCPAP Positioning in Neonates over 32 Weeks of Gestational Age with Neonatal Respiratory Distress. *Diagnostics*. 2022;12(8):1909.
- [112] El Amrousy D, Elgendy M, Eltomey M, Elmashad AE. Value of lung ultrasonography to predict weaning success in ventilated neonates. *Pediatric Pulmonology*. 2020;55(9):2452–2456.
- [113] Liang Z, Meng Q, You C, Wu B, Li X, Wu Q. Roles of lung ultrasound score in the extubation failure from mechanical ventilation among premature infants with neonatal respiratory distress syndrome. *Frontiers in Pediatrics*. 2021;p. 1368.
- [114] Soliman RM, Elsayed Y, Said RN, Abdulbaqi AM, Hashem RH, Aly H. Prediction of extubation readiness using lung ultrasound in preterm infants. *Pediatric Pulmonology*. 2021;56(7):2073–2080.
- [115] Giorno EP, Foronda FK, De Paulis M, Ghosn DSB, Couto TB, Sa FV, et al. Point-of-care lung ultrasound score for predicting escalated care in children with respiratory distress. *The American Journal of Emergency Medicine*. 2023;68:112–118.

- [116] Niyogi SG, Kumar B, Puri GD, Negi S, Mishra AK, Thingnam SKS. Utility of lung ultrasound in the estimation of extravascular lung water in a pediatric population—a prospective observational study. *Journal of Cardiothoracic and Vascular Anesthesia*. 2022;36(8):2385–2392.
- [117] Liu J. The lung ultrasound score cannot accurately evaluate the severity of neonatal lung disease. *Journal of Ultrasound in Medicine*. 2020;39(5):1015–1020.
- [118] Hoshino Y, Arai J, Hirono K, Maruo K, Kajikawa D, Yukitake Y, et al. Gravity-induced loss of aeration and atelectasis development in the preterm lung: a serial sonographic assessment. *Journal of Perinatology*. 2022;42(2):231–236.
- [119] Loi B, Regiroli G, Foligno S, Centorrino R, Yousef N, Vedovelli L, et al. Respiratory and haemodynamic effects of 6h-pronation in neonates recovering from respiratory distress syndrome, or affected by acute respiratory distress syndrome or evolving bronchopulmonary dysplasia: a prospective, physiological, crossover, controlled cohort study. *EClinicalMedicine*. 2023;55.
- [120] Girona-Alarcón M, Cuaresma-González A, Rodríguez-Fanjul J, Bobillo-Perez S, Inarejos E, Sánchez-de Toledo J, et al. LUCAS (lung ultrasonography in cardiac surgery) score to monitor pulmonary edema after congenital cardiac surgery in children. *The Journal of Maternal-Fetal & Neonatal Medicine*. 2022;35(6):1213–1218.
- [121] Szymański P, Kruczek P, Hożejowski R, Wais P. Modified lung ultrasound score predicts ventilation requirements in neonatal respiratory distress syndrome. *BMC pediatrics*. 2021;21(1):1–9.
- [122] Mohsen N, Nasef N, Ghanem M, Yeung T, Deekonda V, Ma C, et al. Accuracy of lung and diaphragm ultrasound in predicting successful extubation in extremely preterm infants: a prospective observational study. *Pediatric Pulmonology*. 2023;58(2):530–539.
- [123] Rodriguez-Gonzalez M, Rodriguez-Campoy P, Estalella-Mendoza A, Castellano-Martinez A, Flores-Gonzalez JC. Characterization of Cardiopulmonary Interactions and Exploring Their Prognostic Value in Acute Bronchiolitis: A Prospective Cardiopulmonary Ultrasound Study. *Tomography*. 2022;8(1):142–157.
- [124] Jiang Qx, Shi Lj, Shen Ly, Li Xq, Huang Rs, Chen Lj, et al. Application Value of a New Lung Ultrasound Scoring Method in Neonatal Respiratory Distress Syndrome Treatment. *Ultrasound in Medicine & Biology*. 2022;48(2):275–282.

- [125] Sun YH, Du Y, Shen JR, Ai DY, Huang XY, Diao SH, et al. A modified lung ultrasound score to evaluate short-term clinical outcomes of bronchopulmonary dysplasia. *BMC pulmonary medicine*. 2022;22(1):1–11.
- [126] Zong H, Huang Z, Lin B, Zhao J, Fu Y, Yu Y, et al. The Predictive Value of Lung Ultrasound Score on Hemodynamically Significant Patent Ductus Arteriosus among Neonates after 25 Weeks. *Diagnostics*. 2023;13(13):2263.
- [127] Pierro M, Chioma R, Benincasa C, Gagliardi G, Amabili L, Lelli F, et al. Cardiopulmonary Ultrasound Patterns of Transient Acute Respiratory Distress of the Newborn: A Retrospective Pilot Study. *Children*. 2023;10(2):289.
- [128] Wang Y, Tan YP, Zhang L, Zheng LN, Han LP, Xie J, et al. Application of lung ultrasound in monitoring bronchopulmonary dysplasia and pulmonary arterial pressure in preterm infants. *European Review for Medical & Pharmacological Sciences*. 2023;27(13).
- [129] Lin PC, Chen CH, Chang JH, Peng CC, Jim WT, Lin CY, et al. Monitoring of the Healthy Neonatal Transition Period with Serial Lung Ultrasound. *Children*. 2023;10(8):1307.
- [130] Sefic Pasic I, Riera Soler L, Vazquez Mendez E, Castillo Salinas F. Comparison between lung ultrasonography and chest X-ray in the evaluation of neonatal respiratory distress syndrome. *Journal of Ultrasound*. 2023;26(2):435–448.
- [131] Vivalda L, Loi B, Bisceglie V, Ben-Ammar R, De Luca D. Effect of preterm chorioamnionitis on lung ultrasound score used to guide surfactant replacement. *Pediatric Pulmonology*. 2023;58(10):2761–2768.
- [132] Alonso-Ojembarrena A, Montero-Gato J, Gregorio-Hernández R, Aldecoa-Bilbao V, Alonso-Quintela P, Rodriguez-Fanjul J, et al. Lung Ultrasound Scores Progress Differently in Extreme and Very Preterm Infants after Birth: A Multicentre Prospective Study. *Neonatology*. 2022;p. 1–9.
- [133] Savoia M, Miletic P, De Martino M, Morassutti FR. Lung ultrasound score follows the chronic pulmonary insufficiency of prematurity trajectory in early infancy. *European Journal of Pediatrics*. 2022;181(12):4157–4166.
- [134] Pezza L, Alonso-Ojembarrena A, Elsayed Y, Yousef N, Vedovelli L, Raimondi F, et al. Meta-analysis of lung ultrasound scores for early prediction of bronchopulmonary dysplasia. *Annals of the American Thoracic Society*. 2022;19(4):659–667.
- [135] Maddaloni C, De Rose DU, Ronci S, Bersani I, Martini L, Caoci S, et al. Lung Ultrasound Score in Neonates with Congenital Diaphragmatic Hernia (CDH-LUS): A Cross-Sectional Study. *Diagnostics*. 2023;13(5):898.

- [136] Zhao M, Huang Xm, Niu L, Ni Wx, Zhang Zq. Lung Ultrasound Score Predicts the Extravascular Lung Water Content in Low-Birth-Weight Neonates with Patent Ductus Arteriosus. *Medical Science Monitor: International Medical Journal of Experimental and Clinical Research*. 2020;26:e921671–1.
- [137] Yu LF, Xu CK, Zhao M, Niu L, Huang XM, Zhang ZQ. Bedside cardiopulmonary ultrasonography evaluates lung water content in very low-weight preterm neonates with patent ductus arteriosus. *World journal of clinical cases*. 2021;9(8):1827.
- [138] Zong H, Huang Y, Huang Z, Zhao J, Lin B, Fu Y, et al. Lung ultrasound score predicts patent ductus arteriosus ligation among neonates \leq 25 weeks. *Pediatric Pulmonology*. 2023;58(9):2487–2494.
- [139] Savoia M, McNamara PJ, Cattarossi L, et al. Lung ultrasound score parallels trends in systemic haemodynamics after PDA ligation: a case series. *European Journal of Pediatrics*. 2022;181(6):2541–2546.
- [140] Sett A, Rogerson SR, Foo GW, Keene J, Thomas N, Kee PP, et al. Estimating preterm lung volume: a comparison of lung ultrasound, chest radiography, and oxygenation. *The Journal of Pediatrics*. 2023;259:113437.
- [141] Alonso-Ojembarrena A, Ruiz-González E, Estepa-Pedregosa L, Armenteros-López AI, Segado-Arenas A, Lubián-López SP. Reproducibility and reference values of diaphragmatic shortening fraction for term and premature infants. *Pediatric Pulmonology*. 2020;55(8):1963–1968.
- [142] Elkhoul M, Tamir-Hostovsky L, Ibrahim J, Nasef N, Mohamed A. Ultrasonographic assessment of diaphragmatic function in preterm infants on non-invasive neurally adjusted ventilatory assist (NIV-NAVA) compared to nasal intermittent positive-pressure ventilation (NIPPV): a prospective observational study. *European Journal of Pediatrics*. 2023;182(2):731–739.
- [143] Singh Y, Tissot C, Fraga MV, Yousef N, Cortes RG, Lopez J, et al. International evidence-based guidelines on Point of Care Ultrasound (POCUS) for critically ill neonates and children issued by the POCUS Working Group of the European Society of Paediatric and Neonatal Intensive Care (ESPNIC). *Critical Care*. 2020;24(1):1–16.
- [144] Pereda MA, Chavez MA, Hooper-Miele CC, Gilman RH, Steinhoff MC, Ellington LE, et al. Lung ultrasound for the diagnosis of pneumonia in children: a meta-analysis. *Pediatrics*. 2015;135(4):714–722.

- [145] Ismail R, El Raggal NM, Hegazy LA, Sakr HM, Eldafrawy OA, Farid YA. Lung ultrasound role in diagnosis of neonatal respiratory disorders: A prospective cross-sectional study. *Children*. 2023;10(1):173.
- [146] Ma HR, Deng BY, Liu J, Jiang P, Xu YL, Song XY, et al. Lung ultrasound to diagnose infectious pneumonia of newborns: a prospective multicenter study. *Pediatric Pulmonology*. 2023;58(1):122–129.
- [147] Liu J, Qiu RX. Lung ultrasound monitoring of legionella ventilator-associated pneumonia in an extremely low-birth-weight infant. *Diagnostics*. 2022;12(9):2253.
- [148] Checkley W, Hossen S, McCollum ED, Pervaiz F, Miele CH, Chavez MA, et al. Effectiveness of the 10-valent pneumococcal conjugate vaccine on pediatric pneumonia confirmed by ultrasound: a matched case–control study. *Respiratory research*. 2022;23(1):1–10.
- [149] Simkovich SM, Hossen S, McCollum ED, Toenjes AK, McCracken JP, Thompson LM, et al. Lung ultrasound protocol and quality control of image interpretation using an adjudication panel in the Household Air Pollution Intervention Network (HAPIN) trial. *Ultrasound in Medicine & Biology*. 2023;49(5):1194–1201.
- [150] Domingo-Alemán P, Sampérez-Sinovas L, Martínez-Tourné A, Puertas-Martínez AI, Martínez-Martínez MJ, Fernández-Fructuoso JR. Early-onset neonatal round pneumonia. *Pediatric Pulmonology*. 2022;.
- [151] Öktem A, Zenciroğlu A, Üner Ç, Aydoğan S, Dilli D, Okumuş N. Efficiency of lung ultrasonography in the diagnosis and follow-up of viral pneumonia in newborn. *American Journal of Perinatology*. 2023;40(04):432–437.
- [152] Liu J, Liu F, Liu Y, Wang HW, Feng ZC. Lung ultrasonography for the diagnosis of severe neonatal pneumonia. *Chest*. 2014;146(2):383–388.
- [153] Durand P, De Luca D, Tissieres P. What's new in lung ultrasound in the critically ill or injured child. *Intensive care medicine*. 2019;45(4):508–511.
- [154] Tusor N, De Cunto A, Basma Y, Klein JL, Meau-Petit V. Ventilator-associated pneumonia in neonates: the role of point of care lung ultrasound. *European journal of pediatrics*. 2021;180(1):137–146.
- [155] Omran A, Awad H, Ibrahim M, El-Sharkawy S, Elfiky S, Rezk AR. Lung Ultrasound and Neutrophil Lymphocyte Ratio in Early Diagnosis and Differentiation between Viral and Bacterial Pneumonia in Young Children. *Children*. 2022;9(10):1457.
- [156] Jiang P, Wei J. The Application of Pulmonary Ultrasound in Neonatal Ventilator-Associated Pneumonia. *Frontiers in Pediatrics*. 2022;10.

- [157] Lin Yb, Xia B, Cao J, Tang ZJ. Ultrasound findings in neonates with alveolar capillary dysplasia with misalignment of the pulmonary veins: report of two cases. *Journal of International Medical Research*. 2022;50(9):03000605221126876.
- [158] Liu J, Xia RM, Ren XL, Li JJ. The new application of point-of-care lung ultrasound in guiding or assisting neonatal severe lung disease treatment based on a case series. *The Journal of Maternal-Fetal & Neonatal Medicine*. 2020;33(23):3907–3915.
- [159] Rebollo-Simarro M, Alonso-Ojembarrena A. Lung ultrasound description of a newborn with bronchial atresia: A case report. *Ultrasound*. 2023;31(2):155–158.
- [160] Tonni G, Rizzo G. Bronchopulmonary dysplasia: Can we provide a link between prenatal and postnatal lung ultrasound? *Journal of Clinical Ultrasound*. 2022;50(9):1328–1330.
- [161] Radulova P, Vakrilova L, Hitrova-Nikolova S, Dimitrova V. Lung ultrasound in premature infants as an early predictor of bronchopulmonary dysplasia. *Journal of Clinical Ultrasound*. 2022;.
- [162] Liu J, Chen SW, Liu F, Wang Y, Kong XY, Li QP, et al. BPD, not BPD, or iatrogenic BPD: findings of lung ultrasound examinations. *Medicine*. 2014;93(23).
- [163] Sun YH, Yuan L, Du Y, Zhou JG, Lin SB, Zhang R, et al. Characterization of lung ultrasound imaging in preterm infants with bronchopulmonary dysplasia. *Clinical Hemorheology and Microcirculation*. 2022;80(2):83–95.
- [164] Xu J, Fu Y, Wang F, Zhou W, Chen L, Liu L. The clinical value of lung ultrasound in premature infants with bronchopulmonary dysplasia. *Revista da Associação Médica Brasileira*. 2023;69:262–266.
- [165] Pieper CH, Smith J, Brand EJ. The value of ultrasound examination of the lungs in predicting bronchopulmonary dysplasia. *Pediatric radiology*. 2004;34(3):227–231.
- [166] Alonso-Ojembarrena A. Lung Overdistention Monitorization by Ultrasound in a Patient With Severe Bronchopulmonary Dysplasia. *Medicina intensiva*. 2020;44(2):131–132.
- [167] Li Z, Mu X, Dang D, Lv X, Si S, Guo Y, et al. Comparison of lung ultrasound scores with clinical models for predicting bronchopulmonary dysplasia. *European Journal of Pediatrics*. 2023;182(4):1697–1705.
- [168] Liu X, Lv X, Jin D, Li H, Wu H. Lung ultrasound predicts the development of bronchopulmonary dysplasia: a prospective observational diagnostic accuracy study. *European Journal of Pediatrics*. 2021;180(9):2781–2789.

- [169] Woods PL, Stoecklin B, Woods A, Gill AW. Early lung ultrasound affords little to the prediction of bronchopulmonary dysplasia. *Archives of Disease in Childhood-Fetal and Neonatal Edition*. 2021;106(6):657–662.
- [170] De Luca D. The promise of lung ultrasound to monitor evolution of chronic respiratory morbidity in preterm infants. *Chest*. 2021;160(3):799–800.
- [171] Sánchez-Becerra JC, Guillén-Torres R, Becerra-Becerra R, Márquez-González H, Ibarra-Ríos D. Targeted neonatal echocardiography and lung ultrasound in preterm infants with chronic lung disease with and without pulmonary hypertension, screened using a standardized algorithm. *Frontiers in Pediatrics*. 2023;11:1104940.
- [172] Alonso-Ojembarrena A, Lubián-López SP. Lung ultrasound score as early predictor of bronchopulmonary dysplasia in very low birth weight infants. *Pediatric Pulmonology*. 2019;54(9):1404–1409.
- [173] Martini S, Gatelli IF, Vitelli O, Galletti S, Camela F, De Rienzo F, et al. Prediction of respiratory distress severity and bronchopulmonary dysplasia by lung ultrasounds and transthoracic electrical bioimpedance. *European Journal of Pediatrics*. 2023;182(3):1039–1047.
- [174] Mohamed A, Mohsen N, Diambomba Y, Lashin A, Louis D, Elsayed Y, et al. Lung ultrasound for prediction of bronchopulmonary dysplasia in extreme preterm neonates: a prospective diagnostic cohort study. *The Journal of Pediatrics*. 2021;238:187–192.
- [175] Oulego-Erroz I, Alonso-Quintela P, Terroba-Seara S, Jiménez-González A, Rodríguez-Blanco S. Early assessment of lung aeration using an ultrasound score as a biomarker of developing bronchopulmonary dysplasia: a prospective observational study. *Journal of Perinatology*. 2021;41(1):62–68.
- [176] Alonso-Ojembarrena A, Serna-Guerediaga I, Aldecoa-Bilbao V, Gregorio-Hernández R, Alonso-Quintela P, Concheiro-Guisán A, et al. The Predictive Value of Lung Ultrasound Scores in Developing Bronchopulmonary Dysplasia: A Prospective Multicenter Diagnostic Accuracy Study. *Chest*. 2021;.
- [177] Avni E, Cassart M, De Maertelaer V, Rypens F, Vermeylen D, Gevenois PA. Sonographic prediction of chronic lung disease in the premature undergoing mechanical ventilation. *Pediatric radiology*. 1996;26(7):463–469.
- [178] Abdelmawla M, Louis D, Narvey M, Elsayed Y. A lung ultrasound severity score predicts chronic lung disease in preterm infants. *American journal of perinatology*. 2019;36(13):1357–1361.

- [179] Hoshino Y, Arai J, Miura R, Takeuchi S, Yukitake Y, Kajikawa D, et al. Lung ultrasound for predicting the respiratory outcome in patients with bronchopulmonary dysplasia. *American Journal of Perinatology*. 2020;p. 1229–1235.
- [180] Walsh P, Chaigneau FRC, Lebedev M, Mutua V, McEligot H, Lam SH, et al. Lung ultrasound allows for earlier diagnosis of bronchiolitis than auscultation: an animal experiment and human case series. *Journal of Ultrasound*. 2022;p. 1–10.
- [181] Basile V, Di Mauro A, Scalini E, Comes P, Lofù I, Mostert M, et al. Lung ultrasound: a useful tool in diagnosis and management of bronchiolitis. *BMC pediatrics*. 2015;15(1):1–8.
- [182] Kogias C, Prountzos S, Alexopoulou E, Douros K. Lung ultrasound systematic review shows its prognostic and diagnostic role in acute viral bronchiolitis. *Acta Paediatrica*. 2023;112(2):222–232.
- [183] Krishna D, Khera D, Toteja N, Sureka B, Choudhary B, Ganakumar VM, et al. Point-of-care thoracic ultrasound in children with bronchiolitis. *Indian Journal of Pediatrics*. 2022;89(11):1079–1085.
- [184] Bobillo-Perez S, Sorribes C, Gebellí P, Lledó N, Castilla M, Ramon M, et al. Lung ultrasound to predict pediatric intensive care admission in infants with bronchiolitis (LUSBRO study). *European Journal of Pediatrics*. 2021;180(7):2065–2072.
- [185] Gregorio-Hernández R, Escobar-Izquierdo A, Cobas-Pazos J, Martínez-Gimeno A. Point-of-care lung ultrasound in three neonates with COVID-19. *European journal of pediatrics*. 2020;179:1279–1285.
- [186] Matsuoka MW, Rocha SMSd, Gibelli MABC, Nicolau CM, Carvalho WBd, Suzuki L. Use of lung ultrasound in neonates during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Radiologia brasileira*. 2020;53(6):401–404.
- [187] Li W, Fu M, Qian C, Liu X, Zeng L, Peng X, et al. Quantitative assessment of COVID-19 pneumonia in neonates using lung ultrasound score. *Pediatric pulmonology*. 2021;56(6):1419–1426.
- [188] Guitart C, Suárez R, Girona M, Bobillo-Perez S, Hernández L, Balaguer M, et al. Lung ultrasound findings in pediatric patients with COVID-19. *European journal of pediatrics*. 2021;180(4):1117–1123.
- [189] Stoicescu ER, Ciuca IM, Iacob R, Iacob ER, Marc MS, Birsasteanu F, et al. Is Lung Ultrasound Helpful in COVID-19 Neonates?—A Systematic Review. *Diagnostics*. 2021;11(12):2296.

- [190] Bogusławski S, Strzelak A, Gajko K, Peradzyńska J, Popielska J, Marczyńska M, et al. The outcomes of COVID-19 pneumonia in children—clinical, radiographic, and pulmonary function assessment. *Pediatric Pulmonology*. 2023;58(4):1042–1050.
- [191] Rankin JH, Elkhunovich M, Seif D, Chilstrom M. Point-of-care ultrasound diagnosis of diaphragmatic hernia in an infant with respiratory distress. *Pediatric emergency care*. 2016;32(10):731–733.
- [192] Corsini I, Parri N, Coviello C, Leonardi V, Dani C. Lung ultrasound findings in congenital diaphragmatic hernia. *European journal of pediatrics*. 2019;p. 1–5.
- [193] Gregorio-Hernández R, Ramos-Navarro C, Vigil-Vázquez S, Rodríguez-Corrales E, Pérez-Pérez A, Arriaga-Redondo M, et al. Lung ultrasound and postoperative follow-up of congenital diaphragmatic hernia. *European Journal of Pediatrics*. 2023;182(9):3973–3981.
- [194] Quercia M, Panza R, Calderoni G, Di Mauro A, Laforgia N. Lung ultrasound: a new tool in the management of congenital lung malformation. *American journal of perinatology*. 2019;36(S 02):S99–S105.
- [195] Merli L, Nanni L, Curatola A, Pellegrino M, De Santis M, Silvaroli S, et al. Congenital lung malformations: a novel application for lung ultrasound? *Journal of ultrasound*. 2019;p. 1–5.
- [196] Filippova EA, Dorofeeva EI, Mironova AK, Kryuchko DS, Ionov OV, Kirtbaya AR, et al. The Role of Ultrasound in Diagnosis of Congenital Lung Malformations. In: 1st LAUNCH, Lung Ultrasound in Neonates and Children; 2019. .
- [197] Yousef N, Mokhtari M, Durand P, Raimondi F, Migliaro F, Letourneau A, et al. Lung ultrasound findings in congenital pulmonary airway malformation. *American journal of perinatology*. 2018;35(12):1222–1227.
- [198] Zhang Y, Lian X, Huang S, Li L, Zhao Y, Lai H, et al. A study of the diagnostic value of a modified transthoracic lung ultrasound scoring method in interstitial lung disease. *Quantitative Imaging in Medicine and Surgery*. 2023;13(2):946.
- [199] Aydin O, Birbilen AZ, User IR, Turer OB, Teksam O. Lung ultrasound findings in children with foreign body aspiration. *Journal of Clinical Ultrasound*. 2023;51(3):447–451.
- [200] Zong HF, Guo G, Liu J, Yang CZ, Bao LL. Wet lung leading to RDS: the lung ultrasound findings and possible mechanisms—a pilot study from an animal model. *The Journal of Maternal-Fetal & Neonatal Medicine*. 2021;34(13):2197–2205.

- [201] Alhassen Z, Vali P, Guglani L, Lakshminrusimha S, Ryan RM. Recent advances in pathophysiology and management of transient tachypnea of newborn. *Journal of Perinatology*. 2020;p. 1–11.
- [202] Liu J, Cao HY, Fu W. Lung ultrasonography to diagnose meconium aspiration syndrome of the newborn. *Journal of International Medical Research*. 2016;44(6):1534–1542.
- [203] Perri A, Fattore S, Prontera G, Patti ML, Sbordone A, Tana M, et al. Lung Ultrasound in the Early Diagnosis and Management of the Mild Form of Meconium Aspiration Syndrome: A Case Report. *Diagnostics*. 2023;13(4):719.
- [204] Regioli G, La Malfa G, Loi B, Vivanti A, Centorrino R, De Luca D. Ultrasound-assessed lung aeration, oxygenation and respiratory care in neonatal bile acid pneumonia: A nested case–control study. *Acta Paediatrica*. 2023;112(9):1898–1904.
- [205] DeSanti RL, Al-Subu AM, Cowan EA, Kamps NN, Lasarev MR, Schmidt J, et al. Point-of-care lung ultrasound to diagnose the etiology of acute respiratory failure at admission to the PICU. *Pediatric Critical Care Medicine*. 2021;22(8):722–732.
- [206] Matsumoto T, Matano H. The still lung point: new sonographic evidence for pneumomediastinum. *The American journal of emergency medicine*. 2016;34(2):344–e1.
- [207] Saracino C, Tessaro M. Pneumomediastinum as a sonographic mimic of pneumothorax. *Journal of ultrasound in medicine: official journal of the American Institute of Ultrasound in Medicine*. 2015;34(8):1521–1522.
- [208] Klavžar P, Plut D. Ultrasound as a problem solver to diagnose pneumomediastinum in an infant. *Acta Radiologica Open*. 2021;10(8).
- [209] Küng E, Habrina L, Berger A, Werther T, Aichhorn L. Diagnosing pneumomediastinum in a neonate using a lung ultrasound. *The Lancet*. 2021;398(10303):e13.
- [210] Wernecke K, Galanski M, Peters PE, Hansen J. Pneumothorax: evaluation by ultrasound—preliminary results. *Journal of thoracic imaging*. 1987;2(2):76–78.
- [211] Dahmarde H, Parooie F, Salarzaei M. Accuracy of ultrasound in diagnosis of pneumothorax: a comparison between neonates and adults—a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Canadian respiratory journal*. 2019;2019.
- [212] Fei Q, Lin Y, Yuan TM. Lung Ultrasound, a Better Choice for Neonatal Pneumothorax: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *Ultrasound in Medicine & Biology*. 2020;.

- [213] Deng BY, Li N, Wu WS, He XG, Li JF, Huang TI, et al. Use of neonatal lung ultrasound for the early detection of pneumothorax. *American journal of perinatology*. 2020;37(09):907–913.
- [214] Rodriguez-Fanjul J, Perez-Baena L, Perez A. Cardiopulmonary resuscitation in newborn infants with ultrasound in the delivery room. *The Journal of Maternal-Fetal & Neonatal Medicine*. 2019;p. 1–4.
- [215] Gregorio-Hernández R, Pérez-Pérez A, Alonso-Ojembarrena A, Arriaga-Redondo M, Ramos-Navarro C, Sánchez-Luna M. Neonatal pneumothoraces with atypical location: the role of lung ultrasound. *European Journal of Pediatrics*. 2022;181(4):1751–1756.
- [216] Montero Gato J, Sacristán PA, Vázquez NL, Martín MdIH, Amorós AG, Fernández LR. Incidence of ultrasonographic signs of pneumothorax in asymptomatic neonates. *Pediatric Pulmonology*. 2023;.
- [217] Raimondi F, Fanjul JR, Aversa S, Chirico G, Yousef N, De Luca D, et al. Lung ultrasound for diagnosing pneumothorax in the critically ill neonate. *The Journal of pediatrics*. 2016;175:74–78.
- [218] Liu J, Kurepa D, Feletti F, Alonso-Ojembarrena A, Lovrenski J, Copetti R, et al. International expert consensus and recommendations for neonatal pneumothorax ultrasound diagnosis and ultrasound-guided thoracentesis procedure. *Journal of Visualized Experiments*. 2020;.
- [219] Montero-Gato J, Rodeño-Fernández L, Serna-Guerediaga I, Aguirre-Unceta-Barrenechea A, Aguirre-Conde A, Perez-Legorburu A. Ultrasound of pneumothorax in neonates: Diagnostic value of the anterior transverse plane and of mirrored ribs. *Pediatric Pulmonology*. 2022;57(4):1008–1014.
- [220] Miller A, Harvey J. Guidelines for the management of spontaneous pneumothorax. Standards of Care Committee, British Thoracic Society. *Bmj*. 1993;307(6896):114–116.
- [221] O'Rourke JP, Yee ES. Civilian spontaneous pneumothorax: treatment options and long-term results. *Chest*. 1989;96(6):1302–1306.
- [222] Montero-Gato J, Rodeño-Fernández L, Serna-Guerediaga I, Aguirre-Unceta-Barrenechea A, Aguirre-Conde A, Perez-Legorburu A. Response to the letter entitled: "Ultrasound of pneumothorax in neonates: Diagnostic value of the anterior transverse plane and of mirrored ribs: Methodological issues". *Pediatric Pulmonology*. 2022;57(9):2259–2260.

- [223] Volpicelli G, Boero E, Sverzellati N, Cardinale L, Busso M, Boccuzzi F, et al. Semi-quantification of pneumothorax volume by lung ultrasound. *Intensive Care Med.* 2014 Oct;40(10):1460–1467.
- [224] Oveland NP, Lossius HM, Wemmelund K, Stokkeland PJ, Knudsen L, Sloth E. Using thoracic ultrasonography to accurately assess pneumothorax progression during positive pressure ventilation: a comparison with CT scanning. *Chest.* 2013;143(2):415–422.
- [225] Liu J, Qiu RX, Liu Y. Case Report: Neonatal Massive Pneumothorax Resulting in Compression Atelectasis Treated by Ultrasound-Guided Pleural Puncture Therapy: A Typical Case Based on Lung Ultrasound Finding. *Frontiers in Pediatrics.* 2021;9.
- [226] Liu J, Chi JH, Lu ZL, Fu W. The specific signs of lung ultrasound to diagnose pulmonary hemorrhage of the newborns: Evidence from a multicenter retrospective case-control study. *Frontiers in Pediatrics.* 2023;11:1090332.
- [227] Dai Z, Lai G, Chen Z, Li Y, Chen X, Lyu G. Double Doppler Tei index combined with lung ultrasound to evaluate the right ventricular function and lung condition in neonates with pulmonary hypertension. *Journal of Clinical Ultrasound.* 2023;51(4):628–635.
- [228] Wu J, Wang Y, Zhao A, Wang Z. Lung Ultrasound for the Diagnosis of Neonatal Respiratory Distress Syndrome: A Meta-analysis. *Ultrasound quarterly.* 2020;36(2):102.
- [229] Ma H, Yan W, Liu J. Diagnostic value of lung ultrasound for neonatal respiratory distress syndrome: a meta-analysis and systematic review. *Medical ultrasonography.* 2020;22(3):325–333.
- [230] Srinivasan S, Aggarwal N, Makhaik S, Jhobta A, Kapila S, Bhoil R. Role of lung ultrasound in diagnosing and differentiating transient tachypnea of the newborn and respiratory distress syndrome in preterm neonates. *Journal of Ultrasonography.* 2022;22(88):e1.
- [231] Deng B, Xu F, Li J, Mai M, Chen Q, Liao J, et al. Case Report: Lung Ultrasound in Critically Ill Neonates With Lung Diseases: Experience From Several Typical Cases. *Frontiers in Pediatrics.* 2022;10.
- [232] Pezza L, Sartorius V, Loi B, Regiroli G, Centorrino R, Lanciotti L, et al. Evolution of ultrasound-assessed lung aeration and gas exchange in respiratory distress syndrome and transient tachypnea of the neonate. *The Journal of Pediatrics.* 2023;256:44–52.

- [233] Kartikeswar GAP, Parikh T, Pandya D, Pandit A. Lung ultrasound (LUS) in pre-term neonates with respiratory distress: A prospective observational study. *Lung India*. 2022;39(5):417–421.
- [234] Cattarossi L. Lung ultrasound: its role in neonatology and pediatrics. *Early human development*. 2013;89:S17–S19.
- [235] Raimondi F, Yousef N, Fanjul JR, De Luca D, Corsini I, Shankar-Aguilera S, et al. A multicenter lung ultrasound study on Transient Tachypnea of the Neonate. *Neonatology*. 2019;115(3):263–268.
- [236] Wang J, Wei H, Chen H, Wan K, Mao R, Xiao P, et al. Application of ultrasonography in neonatal lung disease: An updated review. *Frontiers in Pediatrics*. 2022;10:1020437.
- [237] Oktem A, Yigit S, Oğuz B, Celik T, Haliloğlu M, Yurdakok M. Accuracy of lung ultrasonography in the diagnosis of respiratory distress syndrome in newborns. *The Journal of Maternal-Fetal & Neonatal Medicine*. 2019;p. 1–6.
- [238] Xin H, Wang L, Hao W, Hu H, Li H, Liu B. Lung ultrasound in the evaluation of neonatal respiratory distress syndrome. *Journal of Ultrasound in Medicine*. 2023;42(3):713–721.
- [239] Guo BB, Pang L, Yang B, Zhang C, Chen XY, OuYang JB, et al. Lung Ultrasound for the Diagnosis and Management of Neonatal Respiratory Distress Syndrome: A Minireview. *Frontiers in Pediatrics*. 2022;10.
- [240] Zheng L, Jing H, Liu L, Wang L. Feasibility of ultrasound in the diagnosis of neonatal respiratory distress syndrome in preterm infants. *Journal of Tropical Pediatrics*. 2023;69(2):fmad007.
- [241] Huang L, Ye D, Wang J. Analysis of diagnosing neonatal respiratory distress syndrome with lung ultrasound score. *Pakistan Journal of Medical Sciences*. 2022;38(5).
- [242] Raimondi F, Migliaro F, Corsini I, Meneghin F, Pierrri L, Salomè S, et al. Neonatal lung ultrasound and surfactant administration: a pragmatic, multicenter study. *Chest*. 2021;160(6):2178–2186.
- [243] Luo K, Wang H, Huang F, Tang J. Optimal timing and cutoff range of lung ultrasound in predicting surfactant administration in neonates: A meta-analysis and systematic review. *Plos one*. 2023;18(7):e0287758.

- [244] Kayki G, Yigit S, Tandircioglu UA, Celik HT, Yurdakok M. Lung ultrasound (LUS) and surfactant treatment: looking for the best predictive moment. *Journal of Perinatology*. 2021;41(7):1669–1674.
- [245] Liu J, Lovrenski J, Ye Hlaing A, Kurepa D. Neonatal lung diseases: lung ultrasound or chest x-ray. *The Journal of Maternal-Fetal & Neonatal Medicine*. 2019;p. 1–6.
- [246] Atun ML, Fernandez Jonusas SA, Acosta CM. Alveolar capillary dysplasia with misalignment of pulmonary veins in a premature newborn: the role of lung ultrasound. *The Ultrasound Journal*. 2023;15(1):10.
- [247] Xi G, Dai J, Wang X, Luo F, Lu C, Yang Y, et al. Ultrasound performed shortly after birth can predict the respiratory support needs of late preterm and term infants: A diagnostic accuracy study. *Pediatric Pulmonology*. 2021;56(7):2155–2163.
- [248] Gregorio-Hernandez R, Arriaga-Redondo M, Pérez-Pérez A, Ramos-Navarro C, Sanchez-Luna M. Lung ultrasound in preterm infants with respiratory distress: experience in a neonatal intensive care unit. *European Journal of Pediatrics*. 2020;179(1):81–89.
- [249] Vardar G, Karadag N, Karatekin G. The role of lung ultrasound as an early diagnostic tool for need of surfactant therapy in preterm infants with respiratory distress syndrome. *American Journal of Perinatology*. 2021;38(14):1547–1556.
- [250] Perri A, Sbordone A, Patti ML, Nobile S, Tirone C, Giordano L, et al. The future of neonatal lung ultrasound: Validation of an artificial intelligence model for interpreting lung scans. A multicentre prospective diagnostic study. *Pediatric Pulmonology*. 2023;58(9):2610–2618.
- [251] Perri A, Tana M, Riccardi R, Iannotta R, Giordano L, Rubortone SA, et al. Neonatal lung ultrasonography score after surfactant in preterm infants: A prospective observational study. *Pediatric pulmonology*. 2020;55(1):116–121.
- [252] Razak A, Faden M. Neonatal lung ultrasonography to evaluate need for surfactant or mechanical ventilation: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Archives of Disease in Childhood-Fetal and Neonatal Edition*. 2020;105(2):164–171.
- [253] Nair AD, Manchanda S, Kairo A, Bhalla AS. Diagnostic dilemma in an infant with stridor: ultrasound to the rescue! *Emergency Radiology*. 2022;p. 1–4.
- [254] Ma HR, Liu J, Yan WK. Accuracy and Reliability of Lung Ultrasound to Diagnose Transient Tachypnoea of the Newborn: Evidence from a Meta-analysis and Systematic Review. *American Journal of Perinatology*. 2020;

- [255] Li CS, Chu SM, Lien R, Mok TY, Hsu KH, Lai SH. Prospective investigation of serial ultrasound for transient tachypnea of the newborn. *Pediatrics & Neonatology*. 2021;62(1):64–69.
- [256] Arslan Z, Alan S, ALİEFENDİOĞLU D. The diagnostic value of n-terminal probrain natriuretic peptides to differentiate neonatal pneumoniae and transient tachypnea of the newborn. *Turkish Journal of Medical Sciences*. 2023;53(2):486–494.
- [257] Basha M, Kaur R, Chawla D, Kaur N. Evaluation of double lung point sign as a marker for transient tachypnoea of the newborn in preterm. *Polish journal of radiology*. 2022;87(1):220–225.
- [258] He L, Sun Y, Sheng W, Yao Q. Diagnostic performance of lung ultrasound for transient tachypnea of the newborn: A meta-analysis. *PloS one*. 2021;16(3):e0248827.
- [259] Gregorio-Hernández R, Chimenti-Camacho P, Aguado Del Hoyo A, Sánchez-Luna M. A case of neonatal tuberous sclerosis diagnosed by lung ultrasound. In: *Anales de Pediatría*; 2023. p. S2341–2879.
- [260] Aichhorn L, Küng E, Habrina L, Werther T, Berger A, Urlsberger B, et al. The Role of Lung Ultrasound in the Management of the Critically Ill Neonate—A Narrative Review and Practical Guide. *Children*. 2021;8(8):628.
- [261] Guerder M, Maurin O, Merckx A, Foissac F, Oualha M, Renolleau S, et al. Diagnostic value of pleural ultrasound to refine endotracheal tube placement in pediatric intensive care unit. *Archives de Pédiatrie*. 2021;28(8):712–717.
- [262] Dincer E, Topçuoğlu S, Karatekin G. Ultrasonography for Determining Endotracheal Tube Tip Position in Very Low Birth Weight Infants. *Journal of Ultrasound in Medicine*. 2023;42(2):437–441.
- [263] Gao Q, Ji H, Wu Z, Zhao P. Effect of ultrasound-guided lung recruitment manoeuvre on perioperative atelectasis during laparoscopy in young infants: A randomised controlled trial. *Journal of clinical anesthesia*. 2023;86:111075.
- [264] Shady N, Awad H, Kamel D, Fouda E, Ahmed N, Dawoud M. Role of lung ultrasound in the assessment of recruitment maneuvers in ventilated preterm neonates with respiratory distress syndrome and its correlation with tracheal IL-6 levels: A randomized controlled trial. *Journal of Neonatal-Perinatal Medicine*. 2020;(Preprint):1–6.
- [265] Sahin O, Colak D, Tasar S, Guran O, Akin M, et al. Point-of-Care Ultrasound versus Chest X-Ray for Determining Lung Expansion Based on Rib Count in High-Frequency Oscillatory Ventilation. *Neonatology*. 2023;p. 1–5.

- [266] Camporesi A, Pierucci UM, Paladini G, Gentile A, Buonsenso D, Pelizzo G. Lung ultrasound-guided best positive end-expiratory pressure in neonatal anesthesia: a proposed randomized, controlled study. *Pediatric Research*. 2023;p. 1–4.
- [267] Mohsen N, Solis-Garcia G, Jasani B, Nasef N, Mohamed A. Accuracy of lung ultrasound in predicting extubation failure in neonates: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Pediatric Pulmonology*. 2023;58(10):2846–2856.
- [268] Abdelmawla M, Seleem W, Farooqui M, Eltayeb A, Elsayed Y. Prediction of weaning readiness off nasal CPAP in preterm infants using point-of-care lung ultrasound. *Pediatric Pulmonology*. 2022;57(9):2128–2135.
- [269] Liu J, Fu W, Qin SJ. Lung ultrasound to guide the administration of exogenous pulmonary surfactant in respiratory distress syndrome of newborn infants: a retrospective investigation study. *Frontiers in Pediatrics*. 2022;10:952315.
- [270] Lo CY, Le SN, Nguyen CH, Seshachellam V, Kim E. Use of point-of-care ultrasound in the diagnosis and treatment of pulmonary oedema in an infant. *Anaesthesia and Intensive Care*. 2022;50(6):476–479.
- [271] Liu J, Zhao HR, Wei HL, Chen C, Qiu RX, Ren XL, et al. Efficacy of Bronchoalveolar Lavage as Adjunct Therapy in the Treatment of Neonatal Severe Pneumonia: A Prospective Case–Control Study. *Journal of tropical pediatrics*. 2020;66(5):528–533.
- [272] Muniraman H, Chintala S, Richardson R, Duarte A. Successful ultrasound guided percutaneous drainage of pneumatocele in an extremely preterm infant. *Radiology Case Reports*. 2021;16(3):607–611.
- [273] Bloise S, Martucci V, Marcellino A, Mallardo S, Lubrano R. Possible role of thoracic ultrasound in the diagnostic pathway of infant abuse in the pediatric emergency department. *Journal of Ultrasound in Medicine*. 2021;40(8):1705–1707.
- [274] Bassiouny R, Mohamed A, Umapathy K, Khan N. An Interpretable Object Detection-Based Model For The Diagnosis Of Neonatal Lung Diseases Using Ultrasound Images. In: 2021 43rd Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine & Biology Society (EMBC). IEEE; 2021. p. 3029–3034.
- [275] Wu Y, Zhao S, Yang X, Yang C, Shi Z, Liu Q, et al. Ultrasound Lung Image under Artificial Intelligence Algorithm in Diagnosis of Neonatal Respiratory Distress Syndrome. *Computational and Mathematical Methods in Medicine*. 2022;2022.

- [276] He LL, Foo G, Kenna KR, Douglas E, Fatmous M, Sutton RJ, et al. Lung ultrasound detects regional aeration inhomogeneity in ventilated preterm lambs. *Pediatric Research*. 2023;p. 1–6.
- [277] Ramaswamy VV, Bandyopadhyay T, Abiramalatha T, Szczapa T, Wright CJ, Roehr CC, et al. Clinical decision thresholds for surfactant administration in preterm infants: a systematic review and network meta-analysis. *EClinicalMedicine*. 2023;62.
- [278] Nti B, Lehmann AS, Haddad A, Kennedy SK, Russell FM. Artificial Intelligence-Augmented Pediatric Lung POCUS: A Pilot Study of Novice Learners. *Journal of Ultrasound in Medicine*. 2022;41(12):2965–2972.

Abbreviations

BPD	Bronchopulmonary dysplasia
CDH	Congenital diaphragmatic hernia
CDP	Continuous distension pressure
CPAM	Congenital pulmonary airway malformation
CPAP	Continuous positive airway pressure
CT	Computerized tomography
CV	Conventional ventilation
ECMO	Extracorporeal membrane oxygenation
ETT	Endotracheal tube
GA	Gestational age
HFNC	High flow nasal cannula
HFOV	High frequency oscillation ventilation
HMD	Hyaline membrane disease
ICR	Intercostal space
INSURE	Intubation surfactant application extubation
LUS	lung ultrasound
LISA	Less invasive surfactant application
MAL	Median axillary line
MAP	Mean airway pressure
MI	Mechanical index
NICU	Neonatal Intensive Care Unit
NIV	Non-invasive ventilation
NPA	Neonatal pulmonary atelectasis
NPV	Negative predictive value
PDA	Persistent ductus arteriosus botalli
PPV	Positive predictive value
RDS	Respiratory distress syndrome
Spe	Specificity
Sen	Sensitivity
TTN	Transitory tachypnoea of the newborn
VAP	Ventilator associated pneumonia
VSD	ventricular septum defect